

Basel – Socinstrasse 55a, 57 and 59

Resource assessment of structural components

Version 2.1 – March 2023

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Disclaimer: This report is a preliminary resource assessment and should be used as such. The results presented are based on visual inspections and on limited material testing. Material properties and detailed condition of each component should be further assessed prior to any reuse of the components described herein. The authors decline any liability relating to the use of the information given in this report.

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Summary

The buildings located in Socinstrasse 55a, 57 and 59 are three buildings erected between 1960 and 1965. Cast-in-place slabs, columns, walls form the main load-bearing structure of the building. The facade is partly made of precast concrete panels. A new project is planned, and it implies the demolition of building 59 and a facade of building 55a.

Little-known and rarely implemented, the reuse of concrete components from obsolete buildings in new projects is a sustainable approach that promotes a circular economy. When reusing, the components of obsolete buildings are carefully dismantled without being crushed. They are then cleaned, possibly repaired, or trimmed, and reassembled with little transformation in a new project, maintaining their shapes and structural properties. In addition to maintaining the embodied energy and history of the reused components, reuse allows the construction industry to reduce demolition waste, greenhouse gas emissions, and material consumption.

This report is a preliminary resource assessment and aims at inventorying and assessing all structural components of the planned-to-be-demolished parts of buildings situated in Socinstrasse 55a to 59, focusing on their potential value for reuse. Precast concrete facade panels and cast-in-place RC components are included. The assessment methodology, detailed in a complementary report, allows identifying all properties needed to evaluate the potential for reuse of a RC component: geometry, material properties, resistance, current condition, accessibility, future durability, aesthetics and environmental impacts. After reviewing available reports and drawings on the building, onsite visits are carried out to complete the information and visually inspect the structural components. During the inspection, the components are assessed with regards to their suitability for reuse and their condition is classified into a five-grade scale. Destructive and non-destructive investigations are also carried out to verify the material properties and the geometry and rebar layout of the RC components. Concrete cores are extracted to verify the compressive strength, local openings are made in the cover concrete to check the rebar layout and ground penetrating radar scans are done over a complete floor slab to verify the rebar spacing and concrete cover.

The planned-to-be-demolished components represent approximately 800 m³ of material constituting the load-bearing system, with approximately 50 m³ of precast concrete and 750 m³ of cast-in-place concrete. The components of the building load-bearing structure are considered in good condition during a visual inspection and are assessed as mostly suitable for structural reuse. Using the results of the destructive and non-destructive investigation and knowledge on the historical construction methods of such buildings, it was also possible to validate the rebar layout in most of the slab zone areas of building Socinstrasse 59. This knowledge increases the potential for a future reuse of the slab components.

The inventoried components are divided into 6 categories: (1) facade components; (2) slab components; (3) column components; (4) wall components; (5) staircases and (6) timber roof structure. For each of these categories a complete factsheet is prepared, including pictures, drawings and useful information on their condition. The volume and weight of each component types are given, as well as their share of the total material volume. The embodied global warming potential (in kgCO₂eq and kWhoil-eq) for fabrication and demolition of the components is also calculated.

This document should serve as a base for designing and planning future reuse applications for the concrete components extracted when deconstructing the buildings in Socinstrasse 55a, 57 and 59. The information presented here will help planners to prioritize the reuse strategy on the components in the best conditions, with the largest volume share and thus with the largest embodied global warming potential.

Zusammenfassung

Die drei Gebäude in der Socinstrasse 55a, 57 und 59 wurden zwischen 1960 und 1965 errichtet. Ihre Haupttragstruktur besteht aus Ortbetondecken, -stützen und -wänden. Die Fassade besteht zum Teil aus vorfabrizierten Betonplatten. Auf dem Areal ist ein neues Projekt geplant, das den Rückbau von Gebäude 59 und einer Fassade von Gebäude 55a vorsieht.

Die Wiederverwendung von Betonbauteilen aus veralteten Gebäuden in neuen Projekten ist ein nachhaltiger Ansatz, der die Kreislaufwirtschaft fördert, jedoch nur selten angewendet wird. Bei der Wiederverwendung werden die Bauteile nicht mehr genutzter Gebäude sorgfältig demontiert, ohne sie zu Bauschutt zu zerkleinern. Anschliessend werden sie gereinigt, gegebenenfalls repariert oder nachbearbeitet, um sie dann in einem neuen Projekt mit geringen Veränderungen wieder zusammenzubauen, wobei ihre Form und ihre statischen Eigenschaften erhalten bleiben. Durch die Wiederverwendung bleiben nicht nur die graue Energie und die Geschichte der wiederverwendeten Bauteile bestehen, es können dadurch auch Abbruchabfälle, Treibhausgasemissionen und der Materialverbrauch der Baubranche reduziert werden.

Der vorliegende Bericht ist eine vorläufige Bestandsanalyse und dient dazu, alle tragenden Bauteile der zum Rückbau vorgesehenen Gebäudeteile in der Socinstrasse 55a und 59 zu inventarisieren und mit Fokus auf ihren Wert für eine potenzielle Wiederverwendung zu beurteilen. Dabei werden die vorfabrizierten Fassadenplatten sowie die Ortbetonbauteile berücksichtigt. Die dabei verwendete Beurteilungsmethodik, die in einem separaten Bericht detailliert beschrieben wird, ermöglicht es, alle Eigenschaften zu ermitteln, die für die Beurteilung des Wiederverwendungspotenzials eines Betonbauteils erforderlich sind: Geometrie, Materialeigenschaften, Tragfähigkeit, aktueller Zustand, Zugänglichkeit, zukünftige Dauerhaftigkeit, Ästhetik sowie Umweltauswirkungen. Nach der Sichtung der vorgängig verfügbaren Berichte und Zeichnungen zu dem Gebäude werden Begehungen vor Ort durchgeführt, um die Informationen zu vervollständigen und die tragenden Bauteile von Auge zu untersuchen. Dabei werden die Bauteile hinsichtlich ihrer Eignung für eine Wiederverwendung beurteilt und ihr Zustand gemäss einer fünfstufigen Skala bewertet. Ausserdem werden zerstörende und zerstörungsfreie Untersuchungen durchgeführt, um die Materialeigenschaften, die Geometrie und die Bewehrungsführung der Betonbauteile zu ermitteln. Zur Überprüfung der Druckfestigkeit werden Betonkerne entnommen, zur Feststellung der Bewehrungsführung werden lokale Öffnungen im Deckbeton erstellt und die Bewehrungsabstände sowie die Überdeckung werden durch Georadar-Scans einer kompletten Decke ermittelt.

Das rückzubauende Tragwerk besteht aus ca. 800 m³ Material, davon sind ca. 50 m³ Betonfertigteile und 750 m³ Ortbeton. Die Bauteile des Tragwerks befinden sich gemäss einer visuellen Untersuchung in gutem Zustand und werden als weitgehend geeignet für eine bauliche Wiederverwendung eingestuft. Anhand der Ergebnisse der zerstörenden und zerstörungsfreien Untersuchungen sowie der historischen Kenntnisse über die Bauweise solcher Gebäude ist es auch möglich, die Bewehrungsführung in den meisten Deckenbereichen des Gebäudes Socinstrasse 59 zu ermitteln. Dieses Wissen erhöht das Potential für eine zukünftige Wiederverwendung der Deckenbauteile.

Die inventarisierten Bauteile sind in 6 Kategorien unterteilt: (1) Fassadenelemente; (2) Deckenelemente; (3) Stützelemente; (4) Wandelemente; (5) Treppen und (6) Holzdachkonstruktion. Für jede dieser Kategorien wird ein vollständiges Datenblatt mit Fotos, Zeichnungen und nützlichen Informationen über ihren Zustand erstellt. Volumen und Gewicht der einzelnen Bauteiltypen werden ebenso angegeben wie ihr Anteil am gesamten Materialvolumen. Das entsprechende Treibhauspotenzial (in kgCO_{2eq} und kWh_{oil-eq}) für die Herstellung und den Abbruch der Bauteile wird ebenfalls berechnet.

Das vorliegende Dokument soll als Grundlage dienen für die Entwicklung und die Planung zukünftiger Wiederverwendungsmöglichkeiten für die beim Rückbau der Gebäude in der Socinstrasse 55a, 57 und 59 gewonnenen Betonbauteile. Die hier beschriebenen Informationen werden den Planern helfen, die Wiederverwendungsstrategie auf die Bauteile im besten Zustand, mit dem grössten Volumenanteil und somit dem grössten Treibhauspotenzial zu konzentrieren.

1 Introduction

1.1 Socinstrasse 55a, 57 and 59

The buildings in Socinstrasse 55a, 57 and 59 in Basel (Figure 1) are three buildings with mainly cast-in-place reinforced concrete (RC) structures. They were built to accommodate the *Schweizerische Tropeninstitut (Swiss TPH)*. A new project is being realized for the implementation of the *Institut für Rechtsmedizin (IRM)* in the buildings. This involves demolitions, transformations, and reconstructions. This new project is led by Hirt Brunetti Architekten AG.

Figure 1. Socinstrasse 55a to 59 – Location plan

Building 57 (Figure 2(b)) was erected in 1960 and was planned by architects Suter & Suter. It is composed of two underground floors, a ground floor, two upper floors and an attic. It was transformed in 1980, when a sloped roof was added to create the attic. It occupies a surface area of approximately 160 m² (ground floor area). The building system is mainly made up of RC slabs and walls, with a timber roof structure. For the new project, this building will be transformed but will not be dismantled. The historical villa, also located at Socinstrasse 57 and used as laboratory and offices, is not concerned by the new project.

Building 55a (Figure 2(a)) was constructed in 1965 by Franc Sidler Architekt and was totally renovated in 2010. It is composed of a basement, a ground floor, three upper floors and an attic. It occupies a surface area of approximately 380 m² (ground floor area). The building system is made of cast-in-place RC slabs on beams and columns, with a timber roof structure. Cast-in-place walls mainly constitute the lift cages and parts of the facades. Prefabricated concrete components are also used for facades. In the new project, this building will mainly be transformed but part of its southeast extremity will be demolished.

Building 59 (Figure 2(c)) was also built in 1965 by the same architect as building 55a. It is an extension of building 57. It is composed of a basement, a ground floor, two upper floors and an attic. It occupies a surface area of approximately 660 m² (ground floor area). The building system is mainly made of cast-in-place RC slabs on columns, with a timber roof structure. The RC slabs are potentially also supported on beams. However, perhaps hidden in the walls, their presence is not certain at this point of the analysis. Cast-in-place walls mainly constitute the lift cages and parts of the facades. Prefabricated concrete components are also used for facades. This building will be demolished for the new project, including the basement floor.

The three buildings are interconnected. An underground parking lot built in 1965 by Franc Sidler & Walter Dietrich Architekten, is linked to buildings 55a and 57. A footbridge connects buildings 55a and 59. It was built in 1981 by Rudolf Jahraus Architekt.

The demolition of building 59 and a part of building 55a make available a large amount of RC components currently composing the structure and the facades. This document inventories and assesses these components with regards to their potential reuse in a new structure. Only the components planned to be deconstructed are concerned.

Figure 2. Facades of (a) building 55a, (b) building 57 and 59, (c) building 59.

Figure 3 Cross-section of (a) Building 55a, (b) building 57 and (c) building 59

1.2 Scope and objectives

This report aims at inventorying and assessing all RC structural components planned to be deconstructed in buildings Socinstrasse 55a and 59, focusing on their potential value for reuse. Components of building Socinstrasse 57 are not addressed as no parts of this building will be deconstructed.

The methodology detailed in “*Resource assessment for the reuse of load-bearing reinforced concrete components*” [1] is applied here. It aims at identifying all properties needed to plan the reuse of a RC component: material properties, resistance, actual condition, aesthetics, accessibility, future durability and environmental impacts. Rehabilitation methods are out-of-scope of this report.

The complete resource assessment of the planned-to-be-deconstructed RC structural components is presented in chapter 2. The components are divided into 5 categories: (1) facade components; (2) slab components; (3) wall components; (4) column components; and (5) staircases. For each component types of these categories, a complete factsheet is prepared, including pictures, drawings and useful information on their condition. Both precast and cast-in-place RC components are included in the inventory and assessment. These components are part of the load-bearing structure or are self-supporting such as the precast facade components. The following building components are considered as out-of-scope for this report:

- > Non-bearing partitions, doors and windows;
- > HVACS technical equipment;
- > Any electrical equipment;
- > All finishing layers,
- > Furniture.

Information collected on the timber roof structure of Socinstrasse 59 is also briefly introduced on this report. Timber structures are however not the focus of this report.

1.3 Report version

This report is version 2.0 of the resource assessment of the Socinstrasse buildings. The main differences to version 1.0 are listed below:

- > The general structure of the report has been modified. Notably, the factsheets of all components are now found in Appendix 5 - Components factsheets.
- > The thickness of the cast-in-place slabs of building 59 has been modified to 16 cm instead of 18 cm.
- > Since the finalization of version 1.0, an additional on-site visit has been done by the EPFL team. New insights on the static system of building 59 were obtained (see paragraph 3.2).
- > During the visit, non-destructive tests were also carried out on one of the slabs of building 59. The results are given in Appendix 4 – Non-destructive testing report and discussed in paragraphs 2.5.2 and 3.5.
- > The determination of the structural capacity of the cast-in-place slabs of building 59 has been refined and complemented with the new findings (paragraph 3).

2 Resource assessment results

2.1 Preamble

The following presents the detailed resource assessment of the planned-to-be-deconstructed RC components of the buildings in Socinstrasse 55a and 59. Results are presented following the methodological steps detailed in the report “*Resource assessment for the reuse of load-bearing reinforced concrete components*” [1].

The assessment focuses on cast-in-place RC load-bearing structure and facade precast RC panels and briefly describes timber structures. The components are separated into five categories:

- > Facade components
- > Slab components
- > Column components
- > Wall components
- > Staircases
- > Timber roof structure

Each of these categories is subdivided into a certain number of component types, as shown in the figures of Appendix 1 – Location of component types. These types are themselves subdivided into subtypes with the same characteristics but slightly varying geometry. All relevant information from the assessment is summarized for each component type in the factsheets given in Appendix 5 - Components factsheets.

2.2 Review of existing data

2.2.1 Document list

This report is based on the following documents describing the buildings in Socinstrasse 55a, 57 and 59. All other references are given in chapter 6.

Existing plans

- A. Construction plans of buildings 57 by Suter & Suter, 1960
- B. Transformation plans of building 57 by Suter&Suter, 1980
- C. Construction plans of buildings 55a and 59 by Franc Sidler Architekt, 1965.
- D. Architectural plans of the buildings in their current state, by Hirt Brunetti Architekten AG.
- E. Deconstruction and reconstruction plans for the three buildings by Luca Selva AG, architect, 2020

Existing reports

- F. Structural calculations for building 55a, «Statische Berechnung» by Gebrüder Gruner Ingenieurbureau, 1959 and by H.C. Humbel ingenieurbureau, 1968.
- G. Feasibility studies for the three buildings, “Machbarkeitsstudie” by many actors, between 2015 and 2016.
- H. Building pollutants diagnosis for the three buildings, «Schadstoff-Gutachten vor Rück-/Umbau» by Carbotech AG, 2020.
- I. Report on investigations for building 57, “Sondierungen” by Hirt Brunetti Architekten, 2022.

Photos

- J. Inspection photos, 2015

2.2.2 Summary of prior information

The following summarizes all prior and relevant information found in drawings and reports made available while preparing this report.

Existing plans

The construction drawings from 1960 and 1965 [A] and [C] include architectural plans of the three buildings. Most dimensions are available. The dimensions of the facade components are however lacking. The presence of beams under the slabs of building 59 is also unclear from the architectural drawings. Such beams could be hidden in the non-bearing partitions between the rooms.

Incomplete engineering drawings are available. Complete reinforcement plans are only available for building 57, where no parts will be deconstructed. For the two other buildings, no information about the rebars layout (diameter and spacing) is available.

Building pollutant diagnoses

The toxicity report [H] indicate the presence of asbestos in certain non-structural components of the three buildings. It concerns some tiles, joints and glues (bituminous), window sealant and fiber cement boards. Before the dismantling for a possible reuse of the structural components, elements containing asbestos must be removed and disposed of by a specialized company. The removal should avoid as much as possible the production of dust.

Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCB) were detected in some dilatation joints (buildings 57 and 59) and joints between concrete components (building 55a). The number of concerned components is quite small. During deconstruction, the joints should be completely removed by a specialized company, while avoiding heating the joints or producing dust. Contamination with PCBs of the concrete neighboring the joints should be checked by further sampling.

Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAH) were detected in cork insulation and soil joints of building 59. These materials must be disposed of properly by a specialized company, while avoiding the production of dust. Tar insulation, which might also contain PAH, is present in building 57 and may also be found in the other buildings.

For any further information or action to be carried out in this regard, please refer to the relevant documents [H].

Other documents

The other documents listed were not considered for this work.

2.3 On-site visits

A first visit took place on the 27th of September 2022. The weather was cloudy, and it was raining. The following people were present:

- > Christina Bronowski, Development Manager, Immobilien Basel-Stadt
- > Christoph Währen, Project manager, Bau- und Verkehrsdepartement des Kantons Basel-Stadt
- > Ute Lemm, architect, Hirt Brunetti Architekten
- > Martin Schäuble, Executive manager, Basler Baulabor AG
- > Maléna Bastien-Masse, researcher and civil engineer, EPFL, Structural Xploration Lab
- > Julie Devènes, researcher and civil engineer, EPFL, Structural Xploration Lab

During this visit, the facade components as well as the main load-bearing structures were inspected. The required material investigations and their location was also decided. A major part of the resource assessment was done that day with the collection of information: pictures of buildings and components, determination of the color and finishing of each component, etc. The visual inspection concluded in a good condition of the interior components of building 59 and a rather good condition of the facade components of buildings 55a and 59.

A second visit was made by the EPFL team, authors of this document, on the 21st of November 2022. The weather was cloudy and wet. The location of the samplings for the material investigations on the facade panels is then confirmed with the material testing laboratory (Basler Baulabor AG). Information on the geometry and layout of the building structures was also confirmed on that occasion.

A third visit was made by the EPFL team, authors of this document, on the 25th of January 2023, accompanied by Bridgology SA to execute ground penetrating radar (GPR) scans. The weather was cloudy and dry. The 2nd floor slab (slab over R1) of building 59 is scanned and information on the geometry and layout of the building structure is also confirmed on that occasion.

2.4 Investigations on material properties

2.4.1 Localization of the sampling zones

Destructive investigations were carried out on the facade panels of buildings 55a and 59 and on slabs of building 59. For building 59, all samplings were carried out at the 2nd floor. For building 55a, the south-east facade was tested. The zones are localized on Figure 4.

- > Three 50-mm diameter cores were extracted per zone, in zones 1 (façade of building 55a), 2 and 3 (façade and slabs of building 59) to check the concrete compressive resistance.
- > Five 50-mm diameter cores were extracted in zone 3 (slabs of building 59) to check the concrete young modulus.
- > The carbonation depths was check only on cores extracted from the facades (zone 1 for building 55a and zone 2 for building 59).
- > Openings were made (zone1 for building 55a and zone 4 for building 59) to obtain information on the rebars (types, diameters, spacing and cover depth).

Figure 4. Location of sampling zones – (a) Building 55a and (b) Building 59

2.4.2 Concrete compressive strength and Young's modulus

The results of the compressive tests on the cores are given in Table 1. The detailed report from the laboratory is given in Appendix 3 – Material technical examination. Using these results, the characteristic value of the concrete compressive strength ($f_{ck,act}$) is obtained. The concrete young modulus tested on slab cores of building 59 (zone 3) is of **36.2 GPa**.

Precast facade – Building 55a Zone 1		Precast facade – Building 59 Zone 2		Cast-in-place slab – Building 59 Zone 3	
S1	46.2 MPa	S1	69.2 MPa	S1	46.7 MPa
S2	41.2 MPa	S2	72.3 MPa	S2	46.0 MPa
S3	42.8 MPa	S3	62.5 MPa	S3	41.6 MPa
f_{cm}	43.4 MPa	f_{cm}	68 MPa	f_{cm}	44.8 MPa
s	2.55 MPa	s	5.01 MPa	s	2.76 MPa
f_{ckact}	35.9 MPa	f_{ckact}	53.4 MPa	f_{ckact}	36.7 MPa

Table 1. Results of the compressive tests on cores

2.4.3 Carbonatation and cover concrete thickness measurements

The concrete cover was measured locally by GPR scanning and through destructive openings in the concrete. It was measured on the slabs of building 59, as well as on the façade components of buildings 55a and 59. The carbonation depth should have been measured in all those three locations but was only evaluated for the facade components. The values measured for the carbonation depth are presented on Table 2. The detailed report from the laboratory is given in Appendix 3 – Material technical examination.

Components	Carbonation depth	Cover depth
Facade components – building 55a (zone 1)	23 to 28 mm	23 to 52 mm
Facade components – building 59 (zone 2)	9 to 17 mm	26 to 56 mm
Top face of the slabs – building 59 (zone 4)	n.a.	avg. 33 mm
Bottom face of the slabs – building 59 (zone 4)	n.a.	avg. 18 mm

Table 2. Carbonation and concrete cover depths

The depth of carbonation of the facade components of building 55a has exceeded the cover depth in some locations. Due to the exposure to rain of these components, it is thus possible that the rebars are corroded. For building 59, the carbonation depths are smaller than the cover depths, and the risk of rebar corrosion is limited. Corrosion of the rebars of the interior components is not to be expected.

2.4.4 Steel type

The standard SIA 269/2 “Maintenance of load-bearing structures – Concrete structures” [2] allows assumptions to be made about the steel type used for rebars depending on the year of construction (1965). Based on visual inspections and manufacturers, the website steeldata.ch also gives indications on rebars characteristics. According to those sources, the steel used in Socinstrasse 55a and 59, could have been built with Baro steel rebars produced by Ferrowohlen AG, which corresponds to type IIa steel in the SIA162 1956 standard [3], with a design tensile strength f_{sd} of 300 MPa. This steel type is considered for all components.

2.5 Investigations on rebar layout

2.5.1 Destructive testing

The localized openings made in the concrete cover allowed to identify the rebar layout in the main components. In first assumptions, this layout will be generalized over the whole components. The exact layout of the rebars should be verified with further scanning of the components, as it can vary along the spans of the components.

Components	Principal / Vertical direction	Secondary / Horizontal direction
Facade components – building 55a (zone 1)	Ø 7 mm, s_{median} = 200 mm	Ø 8 mm, s_{median} = 130 mm
Facade components – building 59 (zone 2)	Ø 8 mm, s_{median} = 130 mm	Ø 8 mm, s_{avg} = 75 mm
Top face of the slabs, near supports – building 59 (zone 4)	Ø 10 mm, s_{median} = 100 mm	Ø 8 mm, s = n.a.
Bottom face of the slabs, in span – building 59 (zone 4)	Ø 10 mm, s_{median} = 100 mm	Ø 8 mm, s_{median} = 140 mm

Table 3. Rebar layout

2.5.2 Ground penetrating radar scans

To complement the destructive testing and obtain more information about the load-bearing system of a building, a slab can be exhaustively scanned using a ground penetrating radar (GPR). GPR is a non-destructive method using electromagnetic pulses to detect inner geometrical properties of massive structural elements such as natural stone masonry and concrete. The device is moved along a line of measurement (called trace) and constantly emits electromagnetic pulses which propagate and reflect within the different materials. The propagation time of these waves is recorded and converted into a depth profile along the trace. Among others, the recorded datasets allow detecting large defects inside the material and determining the thickness of a scanned RC component, the thickness of the cover concrete, the number of rebar layers and the spacing between the bars. Determining the diameter of rebars, however, is not possible.

For Socinstrasse 59, the slab of the 2nd floor (slab over R1) was scanned by Bridgology SA using GPR. The results are given in Appendix 4 – Non-destructive testing report. Generally, three measurements per direction were taken in every room, one at mid-span and one close to each wall (Figure 5). For every line of measurement, the average spacing of the rebars and the average thickness of the cover concrete is obtained.

Figure 5. Traces for GPR scans on the 2nd floor slab (slab over R1)

According to the measurements, the bottom reinforcement layers have a rebar spacing of 150 mm in the principal load bearing direction and 300 mm in the secondary direction. At mid-span, for most locations, no top reinforcement layer was detected. Top reinforcement layers are only measured over the supports. The results are analyzed in more detail in paragraph 3.5.

The precision of the cover concrete measurement is not very high. However, the results show that on average the cover concrete is $30 \text{ mm} \pm 10 \text{ mm}$, which means that it can be as low as 20mm. In some localized zones, it can be lower than 20 mm. This confirms the measurements reported in Table 2, done in the concrete openings and with localized scanning.

The measurements made on some segments of the traces are difficult to interpret and no reliable information on the rebar spacing or cover concrete thickness could be extracted from these. However, the measurements are globally coherent with what was measured in the local destructive openings in the cover concrete.

2.6 Assessment of components

The detailed condition assessment through visual inspection of the facades is given in the figures of Appendix 2 – Facade condition by visual inspection. Corrosion of the rebars is expected in the facade components of building 55a, due to the high carbonation depth compared to the concrete cover depth and their exposure to rain. The damage grade given to of these components during the visual inspection was therefore reduced by one level. For the other elements of the building, their condition is considered good as no damage is visible.

Damage class	A	B	C	D	E
Condition	Good	Acceptable	Deviant	Bad	Failure

Table 4. Damage class color legend

The components are listed in the following tables, with the damage class ratios according to Table 4. Any openings for pipes in the components are ignored at this stage and only the perimeter dimensions are given.

Category	Material	Type N°	Component type	Condition	Component subtype	Component dimensions	Quantity	Area	Volume	Total Significance**
Facade components	Precat RC	5501	Precast facade panel – building 55a		1	1150 x 2000 x 120 mm*	2 u	2.3 m ²	0.28 m ³	0.04 %
					2	1300 x 2000 x 120 mm*	3 u	7.8 m ²	0.97 m ³	0.05 %
					3	1150 x 3200 x 120 mm*	2 u	7.4 m ²	0.88 m ³	0.07 %
					4	1300 x 3200 x 120 mm*	6 u	25.0 m ²	3.0 m ³	0.07 %
					5	5500 x 1300 x 120 mm*	1 u	7.15 m ²	0.86 m ³	0.13 %
	Cast-in-place RC	5502	Cast-in-place facades – building 55a		1	3100 x L x 200 mm*	18.2 m	56.4 m ²	11.3 m ³	1.66 %
					2	1000 x L x 200 mm*	11.7 m	11.7 m ²	2.34 m ³	0.35 %
					3	800 x L x 200 mm*	10.4 m	8.32 m ²	1.67 m ³	0.25 %

* Dimensions estimated according to elevation plans provides by architects and visual inspection. Because no correct facade plans with dimensions were available.

** Total volume of planed-to-be-demolished components of building 55a and 59 excluding stairs and timber components

Table 5. Summary table of the facade components of building 55a

Category	Material	Type N°	Component type	Condition	Component subtype	Component dimensions	Quantity	Area	Volume	Total Significance**
Facade components	Precat RC	5901	Precast facade panel – building 59		1	5300 x 1300 x 150 mm*	2 u	11.2 m ²	1.69 m ³	0.25 %
					2	4215 - 4570 x 1300 x 150 mm*	18 u	106 m ²	15.9 m ³	2.38 %
					3	3027 - 3750 x 1300 x 150 mm*	13 u	57.4 m ²	8.61 m ³	1.29 %
					4	2735 - 2770 x 1300 x 150 mm*	4 u	14.5 m ²	2.15 m ³	0.32 %
					5	1000 - 1680 x 1300 x 150 mm*	3 u	5.15 m ²	0.77 m ³	0.12 %
					6	750 x 1300 x 150 mm*	1 u	0.98 m ²	0.15 m ³	0.02 %
					7	4215 - 4570 x 1060 x 150 mm*	7 u	33.4 m ²	5.01 m ³	0.75 %
					8	3020 - 3750 x 1060 x 150 mm*	5 u	18.6 m ²	2.79 m ³	0.42 %
					9	2725 - 2770 x 1060 x 150 mm*	2 u	5.83 m ²	0.87 m ³	0.13 %
					10	1000 - 1280 x 1060 x 150 mm*	2 u	2.4 m ²	0.36 m ³	0.05 %
					11	750 x 1060 x 150 mm*	1 u	0.8 m ²	0.12 m ³	0.02 %
	Cast-in-place RC	5902	Cast-in-place facades – building 59		1 st Basement floor	3020 x 200 mm	19.2 m	57.8 m ²	11.6 m ³	1.73 %
Ground floor, 1 st and 2 nd floor					2520 x 200 mm	105.7 m	134 m ²	53.5 m ³	7.96 %	

* Dimensions measured and estimated on elevation plans provides by architects because no facade plans with dimensions were available.

** Total volume of planed-to-be-demolished components of building 55a and 59 excluding stairs and timber components

Table 6. Summary table of the facades components of building 59

Category	Material	Type N°	Component type	Condition	Component subtype	Component dimensions	Quantity	Area	Volume	Total Signifiacne*
Slabs	Cast-in-place RC	5903	Cast-in-place slabs		Orange area L = 2.9 m	160 mm	506 m ²	-	81 m ³	12.1 %
					Green area L = 4.6 m	160 mm	916 m ²	-	147 m ³	21.9 %
					Blue area L = 6.5 m	160 mm	358 m ²	-	57 m ³	8.56 %
					Other area L = var.	160 mm	750 m ²	-	120 m ³	17.92 %
Columns	Cast-in-place RC	5904	Cast-in-place columns		Second basement floor	2870 x 500 x 500 mm	4 u	-	2.87 m ³	0.43 %
						2870 x 250 x 600 mm	4 u	-	1.72 m ³	0.26 %
						2870 x 400 x 500 mm	3 u	-	1.72 m ³	0.26 %
						2870 x 250 x 500 mm	1 u	-	0.36 m ³	0.05 %
					First basement floor	3020 x 300 x 500 mm	5 u	-	2.27 m ³	0.34 %
						3020 x 250 x 500 mm	7 u	-	2.64 m ³	0.39 %
						3020 x 250 x 600 mm	6 u	-	2.72 m ³	0.41 %
					Ground floor	2520 x 200 x 600 mm	5 u	-	1.51 m ³	0.23 %
						2520 x 200 x 500 mm	11 u	-	2.77 m ³	0.41 %
					1st floor	2520 x 200 x 350 mm	11 u	-	1.94 m ³	0.29 %
						2520 x 200 x 400 mm	1 u	-	0.2 m ³	0.03 %
					2nd floor	2520 x 180 x 180 mm	11 u	-	0.9 m ³	0.13 %
Walls	Cast-in-place RC	5905	Cast-in-place walls		2nd basement floor	2870 x 350 mm	12.8 m	36.7 m ²	12.9 m ³	0.64 %
						2870 x 200 mm	7.45 m	21.4 m ²	4.3 m ³	0.38 %
						2870 x 180 mm	4.9 m	14.1 m ²	2.5 m ³	0.46 %
						2870 x 160 mm	3.8 m	10.8 m ²	1.7 m ³	0.26 %
						2870 x 150 mm	7.2 m	20.6 m ²	3.1 m ³	1.92 %
					1st basement floor	3020 x 200 mm	11.0 m	33.1 m ²	6.6 m ³	0.93 %
						3020 x 180 mm	32.6 m	98.5 m ²	17.7 m ³	2.65 %
						3020 x 160 mm	21.1 m	63.8 m ²	10.2 m ³	1.53 %
						3020 x 150 mm	13.7 m	41.3 m ²	6.2 m ³	0.99 %
					Ground, 1st, 2nd floors	2520 x 160 mm	64.1 m	161.5 m ²	25.8 m ³	3.8 %
						2520 x 180 mm	60.1 m	151.5 m ²	27.3 m ³	4.07 %
						2520 x 200 mm	7.1 m	17.8 m ²	3.6 m ³	0.53 %
					Stairs	Cast-in-place RC	5906	Cast-in-place stairs		Stair
Roof structure	Timber	5907	Timber roof structure	Good with some cracks	Column	135 x 135 mm	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a
					Pan	300 x 135 mm	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a
					Diagonal	125 x 125 mm	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a

*Total volume of planned-to-be-demolished components of building 55a and 59 excluding stairs and timber components

Table 7. Summary table of indoor components of building 59

3 Structural analysis

3.1 Preamble

In the factsheet SOC5903, the bending resistance of the slabs (m_{Rd}) is reported. This value is calculated for the 2nd floor slab (slab over R1) and using three complementary approaches: (1) using the minimal reinforcement area prescribed by the codes at the time of construction (paragraph 3.3), (2) redesigning the slabs using the original design method from the historical code (paragraph 3.4), and (3) using the results from the destructive and non-destructive investigations (paragraph 3.5).

3.2 Static system

Figure 6 shows the structural system assumed for the 2nd floor slab (slab over R1) of Socinstrasse 59. The figure shows the floor plan of the 2nd floor and, highlighted in red, the load-bearing walls and beams supporting the slab (located below on the 1st floor). The position of the concrete columns and walls is based on the available construction plans from 1965 [C] and the recent architectural plans of the current state [D]. The exact position and dimensions may slightly vary.

During the visual inspection of the building structure, the presence of concrete beams above the non-bearing masonry walls was verified in some locations. Their exact dimensions could not be determined due to limited accessibility, but the beams have a height of at least 23 cm below the slab. It was not possible to confirm the presence of beams at all locations. It is assumed, however, that there are beams between the concrete columns and walls at most locations to create a mainly one directional static system.

Accordingly, the presumed principal spanning direction is indicated with arrows in the figure. Both the layout of beams, walls and columns as well as the observations made during the destructive testing (see paragraph 2.5.1) suggest that the principal spanning direction of most slab parts is the longitudinal direction of the building. Only the corridor spans in the transverse direction and presumably also the part on the right of the elevator shaft (hatched in Figure 5).

Figure 6. Assumed static system of slab over R1

3.3 Minimal reinforcement

In the 1956 concrete design code [3], the minimal reinforcement ratio for RC slabs was fixed at 0.2% of the concrete area in the spanning direction. With this minimal reinforcement area a lower bound for the slab bending resistance can be calculated. For a slab thickness of 16 cm, this minimal steel area is 320 mm²/m, which corresponds to Ø8, s=150mm and a bending moment resistance of approximately $m_{R,min} = 12 \text{ kNm/m}$.

3.4 Original design method

The slab bending resistance can also be estimated using the design methods prescribed in the historical codes from the time of construction. In the 1956 design codes [3,4], no material or load factors were used as is the case today. The designs were stressed based, meaning that the stress in the steel and the concrete due to the actions could not be higher than a certain limit. This limit was a fraction of the material's resistance. Table 7 shows the design loads used at the time of construction. The slabs should minimally be able to resist to these loads.

Load	Value (kN/m ²)
16-cm RC slab	4.0
7-cm concrete screed	1.7
Suspended ceiling	0.5
Live load according to SIA160:1956 [4]	2
Total	8.2

Table 8. Design loads for slabs of Socinstrasse 59

The 2nd floor slab (slab over R1) of Socinstrasse 59 is divided in areas with constant spans, as presented in Figure 7a. The arrows show the main spanning direction. If simplified, the static system of the slab is between a beam on 4 supports and a bi-embedded beam considering a uniformly distributed load (see Figure 6b). The results for the bending demand m_E due to the design loads are presented in Table 9.

Figure 7. Estimation of minimal bending capacity of slabs: (a) partition of slabs area with same span and capacity, (b) static system considered for the estimation.

Slab area	Span L	Static system	Bending demand m_E	
			Location	Value
Orange area	2.9 m	Bi-embedded	Mid-span:	2.9 kNm/m*
			Support:	5.7 kNm/m*
Green area	4.6 m	4 supports beam	Mid-span (edge span):	13.8 kNm/m
			Mid-span (middle span):	4.3 kNm/m*
			Support:	17.3 kNm/m
Blue area	6.5 m	Bi-embedded	Mid-span:	14.4 kNm/m
			Support:	28.8 kNm/m

*smaller than $m_{R,min}$ (minimal reinforcement)

Table 9. Estimation of minimal bending capacity of slabs for building 59

According to design methods commonly used during the time of construction, for the most abundant configuration (green area), a bending demand of $m_E=13.8\text{kNm/m}$ results in a reinforcement layout of $\varnothing 10, s=150\text{mm}$.

3.5 Destructive testing and GPR-scan

Figure 9 shows an overview of the bending moment resistance of different zones of the 2nd floor slab (slab over R1) based on the rebar spacing measured by GPR scanning (paragraph 2.5.2). The linear GPR measurements are converted into areas of the slab with a specific bending moment resistance by making the following assumptions:

- > Each span is divided into 3 sectors according to Figure 8 based on the bending moment diagram of a continuous beam. As there is a trace of GPR measurement located in each sector, it is assumed that the linear results are representative for the reinforcement in the respective area.
- > The measurements with clear results are indicated in dark shades. For the zones with non-conclusive measurements, the available results are extended (indicated in lighter shades) based on the observed spacing in adjacent spans.

Figure 8. Division of span

Figure 9. Rebar spacing according to GPR-scan for slab over R1. Purple: $s=150\text{mm}$, blue: $s=200\text{mm}$, green: $s=250\text{mm}$, yellow: $s=300\text{mm}$ or more, grey: no reinforcement.

For the bottom layers of reinforcement (Figure 8(a) and (c)), the results show that large parts of the slab have a rebar spacing of 150 mm in the main spanning direction. Based on the observations made during the destructive investigations (paragraph 2.5.1), it can be assumed that in this main direction, rebars with a diameter of at least 10 mm were used throughout the slab. The plastic bending moment resistance for $\varnothing 10$, $s=150\text{ mm}$ is approximately 20kNm/m. In the top layer (Figure 8 (b) and (d)), the observed rebar spacing at the supports (close to

the beams) is also commonly 150 mm but the measurements show a larger variation. In the spans, however, there is no top reinforcement in both directions (indicated in grey).

3.6 Bending moment resistance

Based on the analysis presented in paragraphs 3.3, 3.4 and 3.5, Figure 10 shows the assumed bending resistances in the different zones of the 2nd floor slab (slab over R1). It is reasonable to assume that the slab has a positive bending moment resistance of at least 12 kNm/m due to the minimal reinforcement requirement applicable at the time of construction. At mid-span of the longer spans, the bending moment demand exceeds 12 kNm/m, therefore the bending resistance in the principal direction must be higher. The rebar layout observed during the destructive and non-destructive investigations suggests a bending resistance of 20 kNm/m for these zones, highlighted in purple in This knowledge increases the potential for a future reuse of the slab components.. Certain zones with a span of over 6 m (highlighted in blue in Figure 7a)) are likely to have an even higher bending resistance. However, the available data from the investigations does not allow for a more precise assessment, therefore, conservatively, the same bending resistance is assumed, as observed for the shorter spans.

In the top layer, the reinforcement is only present close to the supports and at mid-span there are no rebars (indicated in grey in Figure 9). The non-destructive measurements for the top reinforcement close to the beams (indicated in pink in Figure 9) were not consistent. It is reasonable to assume that the bending resistance at the supports is equal or larger to the resistance at mid-span according to the bending moment diagram of a continuous beam. However, more investigations are needed to determine the bending resistance at the supports more precisely, if required for a potential reuse application.

Figure 10. Final estimation of bending moment resistance in principal direction (for slab over R1). Purple: $\varnothing 10$, $s=150\text{mm}$, $m_{Rd}=20\text{kNm/m}$, green: $\varnothing 8$, $s=150\text{mm}$, $m_{Rd}=12\text{kNm/m}$, grey: no reinforcement, pink: m_{Rd} unclear, presumably 20kNm/m or more

These assumed rebar layouts and bending resistance values can be extended to the slabs of the other floors which have similar layouts and spans, which covers most of the slab area of building Socinstrasse 59. Higher uncertainties however remain for three slab zones of the building where little information is available, shown in light pink in Figure 11. For these zones, the main spanning direction is still unclear. Yet, based on the analysis made on the 2nd floor slab, it is probably safe to assume that the bending resistance at mid-span should be at least of 20 kNm/m. Moreover, these uncertainties could be lifted by limited destructive investigations to verify locally the rebar layout and the presence of beams under the slab.

Figure 11. Slab zones with remaining uncertainties about their spanning direction, in light pink

4 Logistics

4.1 Deconstruction

Dismantling should always be done with great care, to limit the damage on the extracted components. Sawing the cast-in-place RC components using diamond blades or wires should be the preferred solution. The components are then protected during lifting and transportation to prevent any chipping, especially on the sharp edges.

Maximum possible sawing sizes are first defined based on the layout of the components. If required, this size is then reduced to accommodate lifting and transportation limits. For the case of building 59, the slabs are sawn at the intersection with a vertical support (wall or column) or with a potential beam whose presence is still unclear. The span width of the different slab areas, as shown in Figure 6a, should be preserved during deconstruction. Their length can however be reduced to limit the weight during lifting and transport. The weight of slabs by zone type is given in Table 9.

Slab area	Span L	Weight
Orange area	2.9 m	1160 kg /m
Green area	4.6 m	1840 kg /m
Blue area	6.5 m	2600 kg /m

Table 10. Slabs weight by zone type for building 59

4.2 Storage

If necessary, the components can then be stored until their reuse, in a way that will preserve their quality. The recommendations listed below should be followed:

- > Elements previously used in a vertical position, such as walls or facade elements, can be stored horizontally provided they have sufficient reinforcement to prevent any cracking under self-weight.
- > Horizontally stored elements are simply supported on two points (or more if required by the reinforcement rate) using dunnage wood pieces (or support spacers), thus allowing humidity to evacuate. RC panels should never be stacked without spacers, directly on top of each other.
- > The number of elements stacked on top of each other depends on the lifting capacity on site. However, support spacers are aligned between the different levels.
- > Anchor points remain accessible and are not blocked by the spacers.
- > The storage area should be covered, or the RC elements should be protected with plastic sheets to prevent exposure to direct rain. Any accumulation of humidity should also be avoided.

In a first approximation, it is supposed that approximately 80% of the slab area is reused – the remaining 20% is lost-area due to sawing, to existing openings or to an irregular geometry of the slabs – and that the components are stored on 5 levels. Then, the required storage space for the slabs of building 59 is **between 450 and 500 m²**. If the site and the technical equipment allows it, the elements can be stored on more levels. Based on the minimal bending capacity presented in Table 9, the resistance of the slab is strong enough to resist concrete self-weight with linear support at both extremity of the cut-slabs.

5 Conclusion

This report presents the resource assessment of the precast facade components and cast-in-place load-bearing concrete structure of the buildings located at Socinstrasse 55a and 59 in Basel. Most of the buildings' components are in suitable condition for reuse. The combination of destructive and non-destructive investigations as well as the analysis of the structural system of the Socinstrasse 59 building led to reliable predictions of the expected rebar layout and bending resistance in most of the slab zones of the building. This knowledge increases the potential for a future reuse of these slab components.

The construction system of the buildings at Socinstrasse 55a and 59 are made up of repetitive components that can easily be classified into types, facilitating the inventory and the transmission of information through factsheet. This document should serve as a base for designing and planning future reuse applications for the concrete components extracted when deconstructing the buildings. The information presented here will help the planners to prioritize the reuse strategy on the components in the best conditions, with the largest volume share and thus with the largest embodied global warming potential.

6 References

1. Devènes J, Bastien-Masse M, Fivet C. Resource assessment for the reuse of load-bearing reinforced concrete components. Fribourg and Basel: Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL) and Immobilien Basel-Stadt (IBS); 2022.
2. SIA. SIA 269/2 - Erhaltung von Tragwerken - Betonbau. SIA - Schweizerischer Ingenieur- und Architektenverein; 2011 p. 44.
3. SIA. SIA162 - Normen für die Berechnung und die Ausführung der Beton- und Eisenbetonbauten. SIA - Schweizerischer ingenieur- und architektenverein; 1956.
4. SIA. SIA160 - Normen für die Belastungsannahmen. die Inbetriebnahme und die Überwachung der Bauten. SIA - Schweizerischer ingenieur- und architektenverein; 1956.

Appendix 1 – Location of component types

Figure 12. Location of precast facade components of building 55a

Figure 13. Location of cast-in-place facade components of building 55a

Figure 14. Location of precast facade components of building 59 – South-West facade

Figure 15. Location of precast facade components of building 59 – North-East facade

Figure 16. Location of precast facade components of building 59 – South-East facade

Figure 17. Location of cast-in-place facade components of building 59 – 1st floor.

Figure 18. Location of cast-in-place slab components of building 59 – 1st floor.

Figure 19. Location of cast-in-place column components of building 59 – 1st floor.

Figure 20. Location of cast-in-place wall components of building 59 – 1st floor.

Figure 21. Location of stair components of building 59 – 1st floor.

Appendix 2 – Facade condition by visual inspection

Figure 22. Visual inspection of the facade of building 55a.

Figure 23. Visual inspection of the facade of building 59 - South-West facade

Figure 24. Visual inspection of the facade of building 59 – North-East facade

Appendix 3 – Material technical examination

In the next pages, the material test report prepared by BBL is given.

BBL Bericht Nr. **221068-1**

	Immobilien Basel-Stadt Liegenschaften VV p.Adr. S+A - Hochbauamt Münsterplatz 11 4001 Basel
Objekt :	Socinstrasse 55 und 59 in Basel

Auftraggeber	EPFL Fribourg Frau Dr. Maléna Bastien Masse Halle Bleue HBL 0-42A Passage du Cardinal 13b 1700 Fribourg
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Auftrag	Materialtechnologische Untersuchung Fassadenplatten, Brüstung und Decke
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Bericht	M. Schäuble D. Kumalic Muttenz, 8. Dezember 2022
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*Ohne schriftliche Genehmigung der Basler Baulabor AG darf der vorliegende Bericht nicht auszugsweise vervielfältigt werden.
Die Prüfergebnisse beziehen sich ausschließlich auf die geprüften Proben.*

1. Auftrag

Die Basler Baulabor AG erhielt den Auftrag von der Immobilien Basel-Stadt, vertreten durch die EPFL Fribourg, Frau Dr. Maléna Bastien Masse an der Socinstrasse 55, 57 & 59, verschiedene Untersuchungen durchzuführen.

Bei den Untersuchungen sollen am Gebäude 55a an der Südfassade sollen die Druckfestigkeit des Betons, die Karbonatisierungstiefe, die Betondeckung

Am Gebäude Nr. 59 soll einerseits an der Brüstung am Balkon die Druckfestigkeit des Betons, die Karbonatisierungstiefe, die Betondeckung ermittelt werden. An der Decke im 2.OG sollen die Druckfestigkeit und das Emodul geprüft werden. Außerdem sollen Spitzöffnungen Aufschluss über die Betondeckung und die Art der Bewehrung geben.

2. Grundlagen

Grundlage des Auftrages war die Anfrage von Frau Dr. Maléna Bastien Masse und die entsprechende BBL AG Offerte 157697/2022 vom 29.09.2022

3. Vorgehensweise

Die Messungen resp. Probeentnahmen wurden am 21.11.2022 & 23.11.2022 durchgeführt. Die genaue Örtlichkeit der Probenahmen wurden in Absprache mit Bauleitung definiert und im Bericht dokumentiert.

4. Auswertung

4.1 Rohdichte und Druckfestigkeit Beton

Die Rohdichte- und die Druckfestigkeitswerte von den Bauteilen sind nachfolgend aufgelistet:

Bohrkern- Bezeichnung	Prüf- datum	Proben- alter	Masse (g)	Ø (mm)	Länge (mm)	Verhältnis L : Ø	Rohdichte kg/m ³		Höchstlast kN	Druckfestigkeit MPa	
							Einzel	Mittel		Einzel	Mittelwert
Brüstung B1 (59)	05.12.22	-	941.50	79.6	79.4	1.00	2383		344.3	69.2	68.0
Brüstung B2 (59)		-	946.65	79.6	79.6	1.00	2390	2387	359.9	72.3	
Brüstung B3 (59)		-	945.78	79.6	79.6	1.00	2388		310.9	62.5	
Decke D1 (59)		-	930.87	79.5	79.5	1.00	2359		232.0	46.7	44.8
Decke D2 (59)		-	927.86	79.5	79.5	1.00	2351	2350	228.3	46.0	
Decke D3 (59)		-	921.86	79.5	79.4	1.00	2339		206.7	41.6	
Fassade F1 (55a)		-	938.91	79.6	79.6	1.00	2370		229.7	46.2	43.4
Fassade F2** (55a)		-	955.61	79.7	79.6	1.00	2406	2373	205.4	41.2	
Fassade F3 (55a)		-	927.77	79.6	79.6	1.00	2342		212.9	42.8	

Siehe auch Protokoll im Anhang BK-Druckfestigkeit

Anbei die Bilder der BK Druckfestigkeit (visuelle Einschätzung) Ø 80 mm

Im Allgemeinen erscheint der Beton bei den Bauteilen Decke über 1.OG und Brüstung 2.OG Balkon visuell in einem guten Zustand. Das Zuschlagskorn ist homogen verteilt und fest und kompakt in die Zementmatrix eingebettet. Lunker gibt es nur wenige. Der Beton am Fassadenbalkonelement weist teilweise visuelle Übergangsschwächen an den Zuschlagskornrändern.

4.2 Emodul

Die Emodul - Messungen wurden an fünf Bohrkernen (BK) aus der Decke über 1. OG (2.OG), Haus Nr. 59 durchgeführt. Zur Berechnung der Oberspannung wurde $1/3 \times 0.82$ des Würfeldruckfestigkeitsmittelwert von 44.8 MPa als Grundlage verwendet. Das Resultat der Emodul - Messung beträgt 36.2 GPa

4.3 Betondeckung und Karbonatisierung

Die Betondeckungen (BD) sind im Anhang dokumentiert. An den Bodensondagen SO2 und SO4 konnten die BD-Werte nur konventionell an der Sondage und nicht elektronisch erfasst werden, da der Zementestrich eine Stärke von 9.0 – 10.5 cm besitzt.

Die Karbonatisierung wurde nur im Aussenbereich resp. an bewitterten Bauteilen ermittelt. Die Ergebnisse sind ebenfalls im fotografisch dokumentiert.

Karbonatisierung Beton:

Brüstung (B): SO3 9 – 17 mm (Aussenseite)
Fassade (F): SO5 23 – 28 mm (Aussenseite)

Basler Baulabor AG

M. Schäuble

Anhang

Anhang 1 / BK- Druckfestigkeitsprotokoll

Anhang 2 / Emodul Protokoll

Anhang 3 / Sondagen und BD inkl. Übersicht der Stellen

Anhang 4 / BD Protokolle

Druckfestigkeit und Rohdichte am Betonbohrkern nach SN EN 12504-1 und 12390-7

Auftrag Nr.: 221068 / Attest 1
 Bauherr: Immobilien Basel-Stadt, Liegenschaften VV, p. Adr, S+A - Hochbauamt, Münsterplatz 11, 4001 Basel
 Bauobjekt: **MTU Socinstrasse 55 und 59, 4051 Basel**
 Bauteil: **Decke über 1.OG, Brüstung 2.OG, Fassadenelement EG**
 Bauleitung: EPFL, Halle Bleue, HBL 0-42A, Passage du Cardinal 13b, 1700 Fribourg
 Unternehmer: -
 Auftraggeber: EPFL, Halle Bleue, HBL 0-42A, Passage du Cardinal 13b, 1700 Fribourg, Frau M. Bastien Masse

Druckpresse:	Presse M1, Typ W+B Walter + Bai, 0 - 3000 kN, Klasse 1 (SN EN 12390-4)	Festigkeit: 1 MPa = 1 N/mm ²
Druckfestigkeitsklasse:	Expositionsklasse:	Konsistenzklasse:
Grösstkorn (geschätzt):	mindest Zementgehalt (kg/m ³):	Zement:
Zusatzstoffe II (Filler):	Mindest LP-Gehalt (Vol-%):	max. W/Z Wert:
Anwendung:	Zusatzmittel:	
Betonhersteller:	Betonsorte/ Rezeptur:	
Frischbetonwerte:	nicht vorhanden	Verantwortliche Pers. für die Festlegung der Messstellen: Frau M. B. Masse
Probenbezeichnung:	BK B/F/D 1-3	Herstellungsdatum: - Probenzustand: gut
Probennahmedatum:	21/23.11.22	Entnahme BBL AG
Probentransport:	BBL AG	Eingangdatum: 21/23.11.22
		Anzahl Prüflinge: 9

Probenlagerung im Labor bei normalen Raumtemperaturen und Raumluftfeuchtigkeit

Bohrkerndruckfestigkeit

Bohrkern-Bezeichnung	Prüfdatum	Probenalter	Masse (g)	Ø (mm)	Länge (mm)	Verhältnis L : Ø	Rohdichte kg/m ³		Höchstlast kN	Druckfestigkeit MPa	
							Einzel	Mittel		Einzel	Mittelwert
Brüstung B1 (59)	05.12.22	-	941.50	79.6	79.4	1.00	2383	2387	344.3	69.2	68.0
Brüstung B2 (59)		-	946.65	79.6	79.6	1.00	2390		359.9	72.3	
Brüstung B3 (59)		-	945.78	79.6	79.6	1.00	2388		310.9	62.5	
Decke D1 (59)	05.12.22	-	930.87	79.5	79.5	1.00	2359	2350	232.0	46.7	44.8
Decke D2 (59)		-	927.86	79.5	79.5	1.00	2351		228.3	46.0	
Decke D3 (59)		-	921.86	79.5	79.4	1.00	2339		206.7	41.6	
Fassade F1 (55a)	05.12.22	-	938.91	79.6	79.6	1.00	2370	2373	229.7	46.2	43.4
Fassade F2** (55a)		-	955.61	79.7	79.6	1.00	2406		205.4	41.2	
Fassade F3 (55a)		-	927.77	79.6	79.6	1.00	2342		212.9	42.8	

EN 12504-1: Festigkeitsvergleich mit der Würfeldruckfestigkeit (Verhältnis Länge zum Durchmesser:1.0) ✓

Oberflächenbehandlung: Alle Proben beidseitig geschliffen

Die Messunsicherheit des Messverfahrens kann nach Absprache mit BBL zugestellt werden

Visuelle Untersuchung der Proben bei Entnahme od. Erhalt/ Allg. Bemerkungen

Das Betonalter bzw. die Festigkeitsentwicklung wurde nicht berücksichtigt.

****Bohrkern mit Horizontal Bewehrungseisen**

Ohne schriftliche Genehmigung der Basler Baulabor AG darf der vorliegende Bericht nicht auszugsweise vervielfältigt werden.

Die Prüfergebnisse beziehen sich ausschließlich auf die untersuchten Proben / * nicht akkreditierter Bereich

E-Modul Bestimmung an Bohrzylinder nach SN EN 12390-13 Verfahren B

Auftrag Nr.: 221068 Attest 1
 Bauherr: Immobilien Basel-Stadt, Liegenschaften VV, p. Adr, S+A - Hochbauamt, Münsterplatz 11, 4001 Base
 Bauobjekt: **MTU Socinstrasse 55 und 59, 4051 Basel**
 Bauteil: **Decke über 1.OG**
 Bauleitung: EPFL, Halle Bleue, HBL 0-42A, Passage du Cardinal 13b, 1700 Fribourg
 Unternehmer: -
 Auftraggeber: EPFL, Halle Bleue, HBL 0-42A, Passage du Cardinal 13b, 1700 Fribourg, Frau M. Bastien Masse
 Herstellungsdatum: -
 Betonlieferant: -
 Betonbezeichnung: -
 Sortennummer: -

Prüfdatum: 08.12.2022		Prüfalter: -				
Probenbezeichnung	Druckfestigkeitsklasse	Expositions-klasse	Würfeldruckfestigkeit MPa	Zylinder-Rohdichte kg/m ³	Zylinderdruckfestigkeit MPa	Elastizitäts-Modul GPa
BK 1			44.8	2356		35.8
BK 2				2386		38.6
BK 3				2374		36.6
BK 4			MW 1/3 x 0.82 Obere Prüf-spannung (Mpa)	2429	35.4	
BK 5			12.2	2416	34.7	
<i>Standardabweichung E-Mod:</i>		1.5	<i>Mittelwerte</i>	2392	-	36.2
Geschliffene Prüfoberfläche		bei 20°C +/- 2°C				
Unterspannung: 0.5 MPa					Basislänge: 96 mm	
Oberspannung: 12.2		<1/3 * 0.82 mittlere Würfeldruckfestigkeit			Prüfkörper: Bohrzylinder	
Zyklus: 3er Belastungszyklus					Durchmesser 50 mm	
Emodul: Berechnet im 3. Belastungszyklus					Länge: 146-150 mm	

Die Untersuchungsergebnisse beziehen sich ausschliesslich auf die geprüften Proben

BASLER BAULABOR AG

Tel: 061 467 70 00

Email: info@bbl-lab.ch

Betonprüfung: Messung Betonüberdeckung, Karbonatisierungstiefe

Auftrag Nr.: 221068 - 1

Bauobjekt: **MTU Socinstrasse 55 und 59, 4051 Basel**

Decke über 1.OG, Brüstung 2.OG, Fassadenelement EG

Auftraggeber: EPFL, Halle Bleue, HBL 0-42A, Passage du Cardinal 13b, 1700 Fribourg, Frau M. Bastien Masse

Messgerät: Profometer PM630 AI ($\pm 1\text{mm}$)

Messdatum: **23.11.2022**

Sondagen

Muttenz: 06. Dez. 2022

D. Kumalic

Betonprüfung: Messung Betonüberdeckung, Karbonatisierungstiefe

Decke über 2.OG (59)

Sondage SO1

B, Quer

A, Längs

Sondage	Bewehrungslage und Ø (mm)		Deckungswerte		
			Min	Max	Mitt
SO 1	quer	Ø 8mm	16	26	21
	längs	Ø 10mm	15	27	18

Betonprüfung: Messung Betonüberdeckung, Karbonatisierungstiefe

Decke über 1.OG (59)

Sondage SO2

Sondage	Bewehrungslage und Ø (mm)		Deckungswerte		
			Einzelmessung (mm)		
SO 2	quer	Ø 11mm	33		
-	-	-	-	-	-

Aufbau:

- Linoleum
- Zement Estrich 9.0-10.5 cm
- Kokoswolle ca. 1.0-1.5 cm
- Beton

Betonprüfung: Messung Betonüberdeckung, Karbonatisierungstiefe

Brüstung 2.OG (59)

Sondage SO3

Sondage	Bewehrungslage und Ø (mm)	Deckungswerte		
		Min	Max	Mitt
SO 3	horizontal Ø 8mm	26	56	39
	vertikal Ø 8mm	51	59	55

Karbonatisierung

13 mm Messwert 1
14 mm Messwert 2
16 mm Messwert 3

14 mm Mittelwert

7 mm Messwert 1
8 mm Messwert 2
12 mm Messwert 3

9 mm Mittelwert

14 mm Messwert 1
18 mm Messwert 2
20 mm Messwert 3

17 mm Mittelwert

Betonprüfung: Messung Betonüberdeckung, Karbonatisierungstiefe

Decke über 1.OG

Sondage SO4

Sondage	Bewehrungslage und Ø (mm)		Deckungswerte
			Einzelmessung (mm)
SO 4	quer	Ø 8mm	60
	längs	Ø 10mm	50
	längs	Ø 10mm	50

Aufbau:

- Linoleum
- Zement Estrich 9.0-10.5 cm
- Kokoswolle ca. 1.0-1.5 cm
- Beton

Betonprüfung: Messung Betonüberdeckung, Karbonatisierungstiefe

Fassade Süd (55a)

Abplatzung freigelegt FX

SO5 Fassade Balkon

S05

F1

F2

Karbonatisierung: 23 - 28 mm

Sondage	Bewehrungslage und Ø (mm)		Deckungswerte		
			Min	Max	Mitt
SO 5	quer	Ø 8mm	23	52	41
	vertikal	Ø 7mm	24	44	35

FX: Bestehende Abplatzung mi BD 17 mm

Betonprüfung: Messung Betonüberdeckung, Karbonatisierungstiefe

Übersicht Bohrungen Decke über 1.OG

fc= BK Ø 80 mm Druckfestigkeit

Em= BK Ø 50 mm Emodul - Messung

Linoleum

Zement Estrich 9.0-10.5 cm

Kokoswolle ca. 1.0-1.5 cm

Beton

Name	Datum & Zeit	Modus	Bewehrungs...	Linien	Distanz	Schnappsch...	Einheit
SO5 Vertikal	23-11-2022 15:11	Linie	7	1	1.289 m	0	Metrisch

Ansicht: Linie Kurve: Deckung

Schnappschüsse (mm mm mm)	[Distanz(m) Deckung(mm)]
	L: 1
	[0.015 32.7]
	[0.338 33.5]
	[0.515 43.9]
	[0.719 41.7]
	[0.911 37.5]
	[1.109 31.9]
	[1.256 26.7]

Deckungsstatistik [Normal]

Anzahl Messwerte	7
Median (mm)	33.5
Mittel (mm)	35.4
Standardabweichung (mm)	5.5
Tiefste (mm)	27
Höchste (mm)	44

Statistik der Stababstände

Anzahl Messwerte	6
Median (mm)	195
Mittel (mm)	207
Standardabweichung (mm)	55
Tiefste (mm)	146
Höchste (mm)	323

Einstellungen

Auswahl Messbereich	Standard (AI)
Stabdurchmesser Ø1 Scan-X (mm)	7
Stabdurchmesser Ø2 Scan-Y (mm)	8
Artificial Intelligence / Nachbarstabkorrektur (NRC)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Stababstand a1 Scan-X (cm)	5
Stababstand a2 Scan-Y (cm)	5
Überdeckungskalibrierung	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mindestdeckung	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Mindestbetondeckungswert (mm)	20
Höchstbetondeckung	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Höchstbetondeckungswert (mm)	80
Korrekturwert für Deckung	<input type="checkbox"/>
Korrekturwert für Deckung (mm)	-
Überdeckungsberechnung	Konservativ (Unterschätzung)
Stabposition ausrichten	-
Linienhöhe (cm)	-
Rasterbreite (cm)	-
Sondenposition	◇
Sondenwagen	Ruggedized

Kommentar

[Hinzufügen]

Geräteinfo

Name	Datum & Zeit	Modus	Bewehrungs...	Linien	Distanz	Schnappsch...	Einheit
SO1 quer	23-11-2022 14:26	Linie	6	1	0.856 m	0	Metrisch

Ansicht: Linie Kurve: Deckung

Schnappschüsse (mm mm mm)	[Distanz(m) Deckung(mm)]
	L: 1
	[0.091 22.1]
	[0.286 23.7]
	[0.417 25.7]
	[0.515 20.2]
	[0.716 20.6]
	[0.771 15.9]

Kommentar
[Hinzufügen]

Geräteinfo

Deckungsstatistik [Normal]		Statistik der Stababstände	
Anzahl Messwerte	6	Anzahl Messwerte	5
Median (mm)	21.4	Median (mm)	131
Mittel (mm)	21.4	Mittel (mm)	136
Standardabweichung (mm)	3.1	Standardabweichung (mm)	56
Tiefste (mm)	16	Tiefste (mm)	55
Höchste (mm)	26	Höchste (mm)	201
Einstellungen			
Auswahl Messbereich		Standard (NRC)	
Stabdurchmesser Ø1 Scan-X (mm)			10
Stabdurchmesser Ø2 Scan-Y (mm)			8
Artificial Intelligence / Nachbarstabkorrektur (NRC)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Stababstand a1 Scan-X (cm)			5
Stababstand a2 Scan-Y (cm)			5
Überdeckungskalibrierung		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Mindestdeckung		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Mindestbetondeckungswert (mm)			20
Höchstbetondeckung		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Höchstbetondeckungswert (mm)			80
Korrekturwert für Deckung		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Korrekturwert für Deckung (mm)			-
Überdeckungsberechnung			Konservativ (Unterschätzung)
Stabposition ausrichten			-
Linienhöhe (cm)			-
Rasterbreite (cm)			-
Sondenposition			-
Sondenwagen			Ruggedized

Name	Datum & Zeit	Modus	Bewehrungs...	Linien	Distanz	Schnappsch...	Einheit
SO3 vertikal	23-11-2022 14:28	Linie	2	1	0.143 m	0	Metrisch

Ansicht: Linie Kurve: Deckung

Schnappschüsse	[Distanz(m) Deckung(mm)]
(mm mm mm)	L: 1
	[0.034 59.0]
	[0.107 50.6]

Deckungsstatistik [Normal]

Anzahl Messwerte	2
Median (mm)	54.8
Mittel (mm)	54.8
Standardabweichung (mm)	4.2
Tiefste (mm)	51
Höchste (mm)	59

Statistik der Stababstände

Anzahl Messwerte	1
Median (mm)	0
Mittel (mm)	73
Standardabweichung (mm)	0
Tiefste (mm)	73
Höchste (mm)	73

Kommentar
[Hinzufügen]

Geräteinfo

Einstellungen

Auswahl Messbereich	Standard (AI)
Stabdurchmesser Ø1 Scan-X (mm)	8
Stabdurchmesser Ø2 Scan-Y (mm)	8
Artificial Intelligence / Nachbarstabkorrektur (NRC)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Stababstand a1 Scan-X (cm)	5
Stababstand a2 Scan-Y (cm)	5
Überdeckungskalibrierung	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mindestdeckung	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Mindestbetondeckungswert (mm)	20
Höchstbetondeckung	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Höchstbetondeckungswert (mm)	80
Korrekturwert für Deckung	<input type="checkbox"/>
Korrekturwert für Deckung (mm)	-
Überdeckungsberechnung	Konservativ (Unterschätzung)
Stabposition ausrichten	-
Linienhöhe (cm)	-
Rasterbreite (cm)	-
Sondenposition	◇
Sondenwagen	Ruggedized

Appendix 4 – Non-destructive testing report

In the next pages, the report on the ground penetrating radar prepared by Bridgology is given.

Basel-Socinstrasse 59

Non-destructive testing Report

AK 06.02.2023

Foreword

This technical note describes the steps necessary to take measurements, process data and interpretations for the non-destructive GPR mapping of the building located at Socinstrasse 59 in Basel.

For the sake of readability, the main results are shown as downscaled maps in this document. The scaled maps are provided to the engineering office as individual files.

Table of content

1. Background and objectives
2. GPR survey
 - 2.1. Principle of GPR
 - 2.2. Data collection
 - 2.3. Processing of GPR data
 - 2.4. Calibration
3. Results
4. Conclusions

1. Background and objectives

This study takes place within the frame of the rehabilitation of the building, the laboratory SXL EPFL. Their objective is assessing all structural components of the planned-to-be demolished parts of building focusing on their potential value for reuse.

Bridgology SA was contracted to carry out non-destructive GPR testing of the structures second floor slab. The main objective is to identify the structure's load-bearing system of the slab.

Figure 1 : Picture of the building, source SXL

Figure 2 Situation plan of the second floor of the building

2. GPR survey

2.1 Principle of GPR

The GPR emits electromagnetic waves that propagate and then reflect within the various materials that compose the structure being analysed. These waves are then recorded by the device in the form of a propagation time whose unit is the nanosecond [ns]. Each recording is called a trace. All the traces recorded along a measurement profile form a radargram, see figures 3 and 4. The conversion from propagation time to depth is finally done by calculating the propagation velocity for each material.

Figure 3 : GPR principle.

Figure 4 : Visualisation of a radargram (a) and of the corresponding traces (b) et (c).

2. GPR survey
2.2 Data collection

Data were collected on the second floor of the building on the 25th of January 2023.

A total of 143 GPR profiles were collected that day, they are indicated on the map.

Figure 5 : Data collected during the campaign.

2. Mesures non-destructives au géoradar

2.3 Processing of GPR data

The first step is to 'clean' the radargrams of noise and enhance the contrast to identify the interfaces between the different components, such as the surface, screed, interfaces and the reinforcements.

In a second step, the depths of the different elements are calculated using the propagation velocities of the electromagnetic waves through each material. Here the wave velocity in the screed and concrete was estimated to be 0.1 m/ns according to the usual values for these materials.

Figure 6 : Interpreted radargram

2. GPR survey
2.4 Calibration

Tel: 061 467 70 00 Email: info@bbl-lab.ch

Betonprüfung: Messung Betonüberdeckung, Karbonatisierungstiefe

Decke über 2.OG (59)

Sondage	Bewehrungslage und Ø (mm)	Deckungswerte		
		Min	Max	Mitt
SO 1	quer Ø 8mm	16	26	21
	längs Ø 10mm	15	27	18

Reading: 2.5 cm cover

Reading: 1.8 cm cover

Längs

Quer

Reading: 3.0 cm cover

Reading: 1.8 cm cover

The hyperbolae look similar while the diameter changes. We can't distinguish between 8- and 10-mm diameter.

SO1

2. GPR survey
 2.4 Calibration

Reading: 3.2 cm cover

Sondage	Bewehrungslage und Ø (mm)	Deckungswerts Einzelmessung (mm)
SO 2	quer Ø 11mm	33

Aufbau: Linoleum
 Zement Estrich 9.0-10.5 cm
 Kokoswolle ca. 1.0-1.5 cm
 Beton

SO2

Reading: 3.0 cm cover

2. GPR survey
2.4 Calibration

Sondage	Bewehrungslage und Ø (mm)	Deckungswerte		Aufbau:	Linoleum Zement Estrich Kokoswolle Beton
		Einzelmessung (mm)			
SO 4	quer Ø 8mm	60		9.0-10.5 cm ca. 1.0-1.5 cm	
	längs Ø 10mm	50			
	längs Ø 10mm	50			

Reading: 3.0 cm cover

Reading: 4.0 cm cover

The GPR data in this window is containing a lot of noise, making 2 of 4 profiles not readable.

The hyperbolae look similar while the diameter changes. We can't distinguish between 8 and 10 mm diameter

SO4

2. GPR survey

2.4 Calibration conclusions

- The concrete cover measured destructively and with the GPR is consistent, this validates the hypothesis of a velocity of 0.1 m/ns.
- The concrete cover calculation assumes a slab thickness of 15 [cm], this conservative value was read out from the GPR measurements. An error of +2 [cm] is possible due to the presence of noise in the lower part of the slab, below the lower frame.
- It is not possible to differentiate the rebar diameters from reading the hyperbolae size.

3. Results

3.1 Radar profiles position

3. Results

3.2 Lower frame

<p>Lower frames depiction</p>	<p>Document type : Blueprint</p>	<p>Author : Alexis Kalogeropoulos</p>
	<p>Date : 06/02/2022</p>	<p>Plan No. 2</p>
<p>Scale : 1m ———</p>	<p>Sheet : 2/3</p>	

Key :

- e30+
- e25
- e20
- e15
- e12.5
- e10
- No rebars - unarmed
- ?

3. Results

3.3 Upper frame

Upper frames depiction 	Document type : Blueprint	Author : Alexis Kalogeropoulos
	Date : 06/02/2022	Plan No. 3
Scale : 1m ———	Sheet : 3/3	

Key:

- e30+
- e25
- e20
- e15
- e12.5
- e10
- pas armé
- ?

3. Results

3.4 Lower frame from the bottom of the slab

Rebars picked = 2
Average spacing = 15.0 cm
Average depth = 2.4 cm
Min/max depth = 2.4/2.4 cm

Rebars picked = 4
Average spacing = 28.8 cm
Average depth = 3.2 cm
Min/max depth = 2.9/3.4 cm

The measurement was taken perpendicularly to the axis of the building, and is measuring longitudinal rebar (along the main axis of the building)

4. Conclusions

- The measurement campaign was successful.
- A total of 143 GPR profiles were recorded.
- 2 maps presenting the spacing of the reinforcement and the concrete cover of the slab.
- We did not observed major defects within the slab.
- The data was transferred directly to the civil engineer.

Appendix 5 - Components factsheets

The following pages contain the factsheets of every selected component type.

For building 55a:

- > Factsheet SOC5501 – Precast facade panels – building 55a
- > Factsheet SOC5502 – Cast-in-place facade – building 55a

For building 59:

- > Factsheet SOC5901 – Precast facade panels – building 59
- > Factsheet SOC5902 – Cast-in-place facade – building 59
- > Factsheet SOC5903 – Cast-in-place slabs
- > Factsheet SOC5504 – Cast-in-place columns
- > Factsheet SOC5505 – Cast-in-place walls
- > Factsheet SOC5906 – Stairs
- > Factsheet SOC5507 – Timber roof structure

Type SOC5501

Category: Facade elements

Precast facade panels – building 55a

Location

Photos

Color and finishing

Type SOC5501

Category: Facade elements

Precast facade panels – building 55a

Dimensions

Cross-section

1:20

Investigation on external side of the components for rebars determination: H: $\varnothing 8$ mm; $s = 130$ mm
V: $\varnothing 7$ mm; $s = 200$ mm

The presence of two rebar layers is not verified.

Type SOC5501

Category: Facade elements

Precast facade panels – building 55a

Description

Construction year	1965
Material	Precast reinforced concrete
Actual location	South-East facade
Initial function	Facade self-supporting element
Accessibility	Easy – No further demolition required before
Anchor points	None
Exposition	Outdoor, exposed to rain and water flow
Color	Shades of grey, closest RAL 7045
Finishing	Exposed concrete
Overlays	Type Fixation Thickness
	None - -
Connexion type	Unknown
Deconstruction tool	Diamond saw and hydro-blasting

Condition and durability

Damage class	77 % Acceptable
	15 % Deviant
	8 % Bad
Carbonatation depth [mm]	23 to 28 mm
Toxic substance	None*

Mechanical characteristics

Concrete density (ρ_c)	2373 kg/m ³
Concrete compressive strength (f_{ck})	36 MPa
Concrete young modulus (E_{cm})	n.a
Reinforcement tensile strength (f_{sd})	300 MPa
Reinforcement young modulus (E_s)	n.a

Component	Geometry			Inventory					Environmental impacts			
	Subtype	Dimensions (W x L x T) [mm]	Reinforcement [mm]	Cross-section resistance [kNm]	Quantity [u]	Weight [kg/u]	Total area [m ²]	Total volume [m ³]	Significance	Initial production	Conventional demolition	Initial production
[kgCO ₂ -eq/u]										[kgCO ₂ -eq/u]	[kWh oil-eq/u]	[kWh oil-eq/u]
1	1150 x 2000 x 120	H: Ø8 mm; s = 130 mm V: Ø7 mm; s = 200 mm	H: 11.3 V: 5.6	1	690	2.3	0.28	0.04 %	132	8.28	303	34.5
2	1300 x 2000 x 120	H: Ø8 mm; s = 130 mm V: Ø7 mm; s = 200 mm	H: 11.3 V: 5.6	3	780	7.8	0.97	0.05 %	149	9.36	342	39
3	1150 x 3200 x 120	H: Ø8 mm; s = 130 mm V: Ø7 mm; s = 200 mm	H: 11.3 V: 5.6	2	1104	7.4	0.88	0.07 %	211	13.2	485	55.2
4	1300 x 3200 x 120	H: Ø8 mm; s = 130 mm V: Ø7 mm; s = 200 mm	H: 11.3 V: 5.6	6	1248	25.0	3.0	0.07 %	238	15.0	548	62.4
5	5500 x 1300 x 120	H: Ø8 mm; s = 130 mm V: Ø7 mm; s = 200 mm	H: 11.3 V: 5.6	1	2145	7.15	0.86	0.13 %	410	25.7	942	107

H: horizontal and V: vertical directions

Type SOC5501

Category: Facade elements

Precast facade panels – building 55a

Additional information

Additional note	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > *Asbestos and PCB have been detected in some components of building 55a, but there is no indication of their presence on the facade components. > The reinforcement drawings are not available. One localized survey to determine the diameter and spacing of the rebars was carried out on a panel of dimensions 1300 x 2000 x 120 mm. The results were generalized to all panels. The steel characteristics are based on estimations made in relation to the year of construction and visual observations made on the slabs of building 59. > The embodied global warming potential (in kgCO₂eq) and the grey energy (in kWh oil-eq) for fabrication and demolition of the components is calculated using their weight and the equivalent factors available in the Life Cycle Assessment KBOB database. These environmental impact indicators are calculated using a higher density for concrete, to consider the presence of reinforcement. The exact impacts due to steel are however neglected and the results may be underestimated. The considered factors are the following: Precast concrete element, normal concrete, from factory - KBOB ID-Number 01.042.
Attention point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > The dimension of the components is approximated on the elevations made by the architects. The exact dimensions should be checked. > The average concrete cover of the reinforcement is between 23 and 52 mm. In some places, the depth of carbonation could be higher than the cover depth. It is then not excluded that the rebars are slightly corroded in some areas.

Type SOC5502

Category: Facade elements

Cast-in-place facade – building 55a

Location

Photos

Color and finishing

Type SOC5502

Category: Facade elements

Cast-in-place facade – building 55a

Description

Construction year	1965						
Material	Cast-in-place concrete						
Actual location	South-East facade						
Initial function	Façade load-bearing element						
Accessibility	Moderate – One or two elements should first be removed						
Anchor points	None						
Exposition	Outdoor, exposed to rain and water flow						
Color	Light yellow painted						
Finishing	Roughcast						
Overlays	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Type</th> <th>Fixation</th> <th>Thickness</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Roughcast</td> <td>-</td> <td>-</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Type	Fixation	Thickness	Roughcast	-	-
Type	Fixation	Thickness					
Roughcast	-	-					
Connexion type	Monolithic connection to slabs and walls						
Deconstruction tool	Diamond saw or hydro-blasting						

Condition and durability

Damage assessment	100 % Acceptable
Carbonatation depth [mm]	n.a
Toxic substance	None*

Mechanical characteristics**

Concrete density (ρ_c)	2359 kg/m ³
Concrete compressive strength (f_{ck})	37 MPa
Concrete young modulus (E_{cm})	36.2 GPa
Reinforcement tensile strength (f_{sd})	300 MPa
Reinforcement young modulus (E_s)	n.a

Component	Geometry			Inventory					Environmental impacts			
	Dimensions (W x L x T) [mm]	Reinforcement [mm]	Cross-section resistance [kNm]	Quantity [m]	Weight [kg/m]	Total area [m ²]	Total volume [m ³]	Significance	Initial production [kgCO ₂ -eq/m]	Conventional demolition [kgCO ₂ -eq/m]	Initial production [kWh oil-eq/m]	Conventional demolition [kWh oil-eq/m]
1	3100 x L x 200	n.a	n.a	18.2	1550	56.4	11.3	1.66 %	138	15.5	191	80.6
2	1000 x L x 200	n.a	n.a	11.7	500	11.7	2.34	0.35 %	44.5	5.0	61.5	26.0
3	800 x L x 200	n.a	n.a	10.4	400	8.32	1.67	0.25 %	35.6	4.0	49.2	20.8

Type SOC5502

Category: Facade elements

Cast-in-place facade – building 55a

Additional information

Additional note	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > *Asbestos and PCB have been detected in some components of building 55a, but there is no indication of their presence on the facade components. > **The material investigations and assumptions were carried out for the cast-in-place slab components of building 59. It is assumed that the cast-in-place concrete and the steel types are similar for building 55a, as both buildings were built the same year. > The embodied global warming potential (in kgCO₂eq) and the grey energy (in kWh oil-eq) for fabrication and demolition of the components is calculated using their weight and the equivalent factors available in the Life Cycle Assessment KBOB database. These environmental impact indicators are calculated using a higher density for concrete, to consider the presence of reinforcement. The exact impacts due to steel are however neglected and the results may be underestimated. The considered factors are the following: Concrete for buildings (without reinforcement) - KBOB ID-Number 01.002
Attention point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > The dimension of the components is approximated on the elevations made by the architects. The exact dimensions should be checked. > The carbonation depth was not measured. It can't be excluded that the rebars are slightly corroded in some areas if the carbonation depth is higher than the cover concrete depth over the rebars.

Type SOC5901

Category: Facade components

Precast facade panels – building 59

Location

Location plan for the North-East facade. The location of the components for the other facades is available in the appendix of the report.

Photos

Color and finishing

Type SOC5901

Category: Facade components

Precast facade panels – building 59

Dimensions

Cross-section

1:20

Investigation on external side of the components for rebars determination: H: $\varnothing 8$ mm; s=130 mm
V: $\varnothing 8$ mm; s = 75 mm

The presence of two rebar layers is not verified.

Type SOC5901

Category: Facade components

Precast facade panels – building 59

Description

Construction year	1965		
Material	Precast reinforced concrete		
Actual location	All facades of the building		
Initial function	Facade load-bearing component		
Accessibility	Easy – No further demolition required before		
Anchor points	None		
Exposition	Outside, exposed to rain and water flow		
Color	Beige, closest RAL 1015		
Finishing	Painting and horizontal wood plank patterns		
Overlays	Type	Fixation	Thickness
	None	-	-
Connexion type	Unknown		
Deconstruction tool	Diamond saw and hydro-blasting		

Condition and durability

Damage class	42 % Good
	31 % Acceptable
	3 % Deviant
	24 % Unknown
Carbonatation depth [mm]	9 to 17 mm
Toxic substance	None

Mechanical characteristics

Concrete density (ρ_c)	2387 kg/m ³
Concrete compressive strength (f_{ck})	53 MPa
Concrete young modulus (E_{cm})	n.a
Reinforcement tensile strength (f_{sd})	300 MPa
Reinforcement young modulus (E_s)	n.a

Component	Geometry			Inventory					Environmental impacts			
	Subtype	Dimensions (W x L x T) [mm]	Reinforcement [mm]	Cross-section resistance [kNm]	Quantity [u]	Weight [kg/u]	Total area [m ²]	Total volume [m ³]	Significance	Initial production		Conventional demolition
[kgCO ₂ -eq/u]										[kWh oil-eq/u]	[kgCO ₂ -eq/u]	[kWh oil-eq/u]
1	5300 x 1300 x 150	H: Ø8mm; s=130 mm V: Ø8mm; s= 75 mm	H: 14.1 V: 24.5	2	2107	11.2	1.69	0.25 %	402	25.3	925	105
2	4215 - 4570 x 1300 x 150	H: Ø8mm; s= 130 mm V: Ø8mm; s= 75 mm	H: 14.1 V: 24.5	18	2208 - 2228	106	15.9	2.38 %	492 - 425	24.7 - 26.7	902 - 978	103 - 111
3	3027 - 3750 x 1300 x 150	H: Ø8mm; s= 130 mm V: Ø8mm; s= 75 mm	H: 14.1 V: 24.5	13	1514 - 1828	57.4	8.61	1.29 %	281 - 349	17.7 - 21.9	646 - 802	73.6 - 91.4
4	2735 - 2770 x 1300 x 150	H: Ø8mm; s= 130 mm V: Ø8mm; s= 75 mm	H: 14.1 V: 24.5	4	1350 - 1333	14.	2.15	0.32 %	255 - 258	16.0- 16.2	585 - 592	66.6 - 67.5
5	1000 – 1680 x 1300 x 150	H: Ø 8mm; s= 130 mm V: Ø 8mm; s= 75 mm	H: 14.1 V: 24.5	3	488 - 819	5.15	0.77	0.12 %	93 - 156	5.85 - 9.8	214 - 359	24 - 40
6	750 x 1300 x 150	H: Ø 8mm; s= 130 mm V: Ø 8mm; s= 75 mm	H: 14.1 V: 24.5	1	365	0.98	0.15	0.02 %	69.8	4.39	161	18.3
7	4215 - 4570 x 1060 x 150	H: Ø 8mm; s= 130 mm V: Ø 8mm; s= 75 mm	H: 14.1 V: 24.5	7	1675 - 1816	33.4	5.01	0.75 %	320 - 347	21.4 - 23.3	735 - 797	83.7 - 90.8
8	3020 - 3750 x 1060 x 150	H: Ø 8mm; s= 130 mm V: Ø 8mm; s= 75 mm	H: 14.1 V: 24.5	5	1200 - 1567	18.6	2.79	0.42 %	229 - 299	14.4 - 18.8	527 - 688	60.0 - 74.5

Type SOC5901

Category: Facade components

Precast facade panels – building 59

Component	Geometry			Inventory					Environmental impacts			
	Subtype	Dimensions (W x L x T) [mm]	Reinforcement [mm]	Cross-section resistance [kNm]	Quantity [u]	Weight [kg/u]	Total area [m ²]	Total volume [m ³]	Significance	Initial production [kgCO ₂ -eq/u]	Conventional demolition [kgCO ₂ -eq/u]	Initial production [kWh oil-eq/u]
9	2725 - 2770 x 1060 x 180	H: Ø 8mm; s = 130 mm V: Ø 8mm; s = 75 mm	H: 14.1 V: 24.5	2	1083 - 1101	5.83	0.87	0.13 %	207 - 210	12.0 - 13.2	476 - 483	54.2 - 55.0
10	1000 – 1280 x 1060 x 180	H: Ø 8mm; s = 130 mm V: Ø 8mm; s = 75 mm	H: 14.1 V: 24.5	2	398 - 509	2.4	0.36	0.05 %	75.9 - 97.1	4.77 - 6.1	174 - 223	19.8 - 25.4
11	750 x 1060 x 180	H: Ø 8mm; s = 130 mm V: Ø 8mm; s = 75 mm	H: 14.1 V: 24.5	1	298	0.8	0.12	0.02 %	56.9	3.58	131	14.9

Additional information

Additional note

- > The reinforcement drawings are not available. One localized survey to determine the diameter and spacing of the rebars was carried out on a panel of dimensions 4545 x 1300 x 180 mm. The results were generalized to all panels. The steel characteristics are based on estimations made in relation to the year of construction and visual observations made on the slabs of building 59.
- > The embodied global warming potential (in kgCO₂eq) and the grey energy (in kWh oil-eq) for fabrication and demolition of the components is calculated using their weight and the equivalent factors available in the Life Cycle Assessment KBOB database. These environmental impact indicators are calculated using a higher density for concrete, to consider the presence of reinforcement. The exact impacts due to steel are however neglected and the results may be underestimated. The considered factors are the following: Precast concrete component, normal concrete, from factory - KBOB ID-Number 01.042.

Attention point

- > The dimension of the components is measured on the elevations of the architects. The exact dimensions are to be checked.

Type SOC5902

Category: Facade components

Cast-in-place facade – building 59

Location

Location plan for the first floor. The location of the components for the other floors is available in the appendix of the report.

Photos

Color and finishing

Type SOC5902

Category: Facade components

Cast-in-place facade – building 59

Description

Construction year	1965						
Material	Cas-in-place reinforced concrete						
Actual location	All facades of the building						
Initial function	Façade self-supporting component						
Accessibility	Moderate – One or two components are first removed						
Anchor points	None						
Exposition	Outdoor, exposed to rain and water flow						
Color	Light beige, closest RAL 1015						
Finishing	Roughcast						
Overlays	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Type</th> <th>Fixation</th> <th>Thickness</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Roughcast</td> <td>-</td> <td>n.a.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Type	Fixation	Thickness	Roughcast	-	n.a.
Type	Fixation	Thickness					
Roughcast	-	n.a.					
Connexion type	Monolithic connection to slabs and walls						
Deconstruction tool	Diamond saw or hydro-blasting						

Condition and durability

Damage assessment	100 % good
Carbonatation depth [mm]	n.a
Toxic substance	Asbestos*, PAH**

Mechanical characteristics***

Concrete density (ρ_c)	2350 kg/m ³
Concrete compressive strength (f_{ck})	37 MPa
Concrete young modulus (E_{cm})	36.2 GPa
Reinforcement tensile strength (f_{sd})	300 MPa
Reinforcement young modulus (E_s)	n.a

Component	Geometry			Inventory					Environmental impacts					
	Dimensions (W x L x T) [mm]	Reinforcement [mm]	Cross-section resistance [kNm]	Quantity [m]	Weight [kg/m]	Total area [m ²]	Total volume [m ³]	Significance	Initial production	Conventional demolition	Dismantling by sawing	Initial production	Conventional demolition	Dismantling by sawing
Subtype									[kgCO2-eq/m]			[kWh oil-eq/m]		
1 st Basement floor	3020 x 200	n.a	n.a	19.2	1510	57.8	11.6	1.73 %	134	19.6	0.049	186	78.5	3.08
Ground floor, 1 st and 2 nd floor	2520 x 200	n.a	n.a	105.7	1260	134	53.3	7.96 %	112	16.4	0.049	155	65.6	3.08

Type SOC5902

Category: Facade components

Cast-in-place facade – building 59

Additional information

Additional note	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > * Asbestos is found in the window frames; these must be removed prior to the deconstruction of the panels. > ** PAH may be present in the cork insulation > *** The material investigations and assumptions were carried out for the cast-in-place slab components of building 59. It is assumed that the cast-in-place concrete and the steel types are the same for all components of this building. > The embodied global warming potential (in kgCO₂eq) and the grey energy (in kWh oil-eq) for fabrication and demolition of the components is calculated using their weight and the equivalent factors available in the Life Cycle Assessment KBOB database. These environmental impact indicators are calculated using a higher density for concrete, to consider the presence of reinforcement. The exact impacts due to steel are however neglected and the results may be underestimated. The considered factors are the following: Concrete for buildings (without reinforcement) - KBOB ID-Number 01.002.
Attention point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > The condition of these façade components is assumed to be good. However, because of the overlay over the concrete, their exact condition could not be assessed.

Type SOC5903

Category: Slab components

Cast-in-place slabs

Location

Location plan for the second floor.

Photos

Overlays

Floor surface coating

Suspended or acoustic ceiling type

Type SOC5903

Category: Slab components

Cast-in-place slabs

Description

Construction year	1965		
Material	Cast-in-place reinforced concrete		
Actual location	All floors		
Initial function	Slab load-bearing component		
Accessibility	Difficult – 3 & more component to dismantle before		
Anchor points	None		
Exposition	Inside, not exposed		
Color	Shade of grey		
Finishing	Horizontal wood plank patterns		
Overlays	Type	Fixation	Thickness
Upper surface	Multiple color linoleum	Unknown	Unknown
	Cement screed		9.0 - 10.5 cm
	Coconut wool		1.0 – 1.4 cm
Lower surface	Metal suspended ceiling or plaster acoustic ceiling		Unknown
Connexion type	Monolithic connexion with facades, walls and columns		
Deconstruction tool	Diamond saw or hydro-blasting		

Condition and durability

Damage assessment	100 % good
Carbonatation depth [mm]	n.a
Toxic substance	Asbestos*, PCB**

Mechanical characteristics

Concrete density (ρ_c)	2350 kg/m ³
Concrete compressive strength (f_{ck})	37 MPa
Concrete young modulus (E_{cm})	36.2 GPa
Reinforcement tensile strength (f_{sd})	300 MPa
Reinforcement young modulus (E_s)	n.a

Component	Geometry			Inventory				Environmental impacts			
	Dimensions (T) [mm]	Reinforcement [mm] ***	Cross-section resistance [kNm] ***	Quantity [m ²]	Weight [kg/ m ²]	Total volume [m ³]	Volume significance	Initial production [kgCO ₂ -eq/ m ²]	Conventional demolition [kgCO ₂ -eq/ m ²]	Initial production [kWh oil-eq/ m ²]	Conventional demolition [kWh oil-eq/ m ²]
Orange area L=2.9 m	160	Mid-span: L: Ø10; s = 150 T: Ø8; s = 150	Mid-span: L: 20.0 T: 12.0	506	400	81	12.1 %	36	52	49	20.8
Green area L=4.6 m	160	Mid-span: L: Ø10; s = 150 T: Ø8; s = 150	Mid-span: L: 20.0 T: 12.0	916	400	147	21.9 %	36	52	49	20.8
Blue area L = 6.5 m	160	Mid-span: L: Ø10; s = 150 T: Ø8; s = 150	Mid-span: L: 20.0 T: 12.0	358	400	57	8.56 %	36	52	49	20.8
Others L = var.	160	Mid-span: L: Ø10; s = 150 T: Ø8; s = 150	Mid-span: L: 20.0 T: 12.0	750	400	120	17.9 %	36	52	49	20.8

L: longitudinal and T: transversal directions

Type SOC5903

Category: Slab components

Cast-in-place slabs

Additional information

Additional note	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > *There may be asbestos in the floor coatings and in the bituminous joint of the 2nd basement floor. > ** PCB is present in the mastic of the expansion joint of the 2nd basement floor. This joint should be removed with care by a specialized company prior to deconstruction. > ***The cross-section resistance is estimated based on the combination of minimal reinforcement, bending demand in donor building, and destructive testing and GPR-scan. The negative bending resistance is unclear. For more information, see the related report. > Two localized surveys were made on the slabs to identify the rebar diameter and spacing. One on the upper face of the slab and the other on the lower face. It is assumed that the layout is the same for all slabs, but this should be further verified in case of reuse. > The steel characteristics are based on estimations made in relation to the year of construction and visual observations in the surveys. > The embodied global warming potential (in kgCO₂eq) and the grey energy (in kWh oil-eq) for fabrication and demolition of the components is calculated using their weight and the equivalent factors available in the Life Cycle Assessment KBOB database. These environmental impact indicators are calculated using a higher density for concrete, to consider the presence of reinforcement. The exact impacts due to steel are however neglected and the results may be underestimated. The considered factors are the following: Concrete for buildings (without reinforcement) - KBOB ID-Number 01.002.
Attention point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > On the lower face of the slab, the concrete cover depth was measured equal to 15-27 mm only. > On the upper face of the slab, the cover depth was measured equal to 50-60 mm.

Type SOC5904

Category: Column components

Cast-in-place columns

Location

Location plan for the first floor. The location of the components for the other floors is available in the appendix of the report.

Photos, color and finishing

Most of the columns are hidden in the walls. See factsheets SOC5905_Walls cast-in-place

Type SOC5904

Category: Column components

Cast-in-place columns

Description

Construction year	1965		
Material	Cast-in-place reinforced concrete		
Actual location	All floors		
Initial function	Column load-bearing component		
Accessibility	Difficult – 3 & more component to dismantle before		
Anchor points	None		
Exposition	Inside, not exposed		
Color	White on most surfaces		
Finishing	Roughcast		
Overlays	Type	Fixation	Thickness
	Roughcast	-	n.a.
Connexion type	Monolithic connexion with slabs		
Deconstruction tool	Diamond saw or hydro-blasting		

Condition and durability

Damage assessment	100% good
Carbonatation depth [mm]	n.a.
Toxic substance	None

Mechanical characteristics*

Concrete density (ρ_c)	2350 kg/m ³
Concrete compressive strength (f_{ck})	37 MPa
Concrete young modulus (E_{cm})	36.2 GPa
Reinforcement tensile strength (f_{sd})	300 MPa
Reinforcement young modulus (E_s)	n.a.

Component	Geometry			Inventory				Environmental impacts					
	Dimensions (H x W x T) [mm]	Reinforcement [mm]	Cross-section resistance [kNm]	Quantity [u]	Weight [kg/u]	Total volume [m ³]	Volume significance	Initial production	Conventional demolition	Dismantling by sawing	Initial production	Conventional demolition	Dismantling by sawing
Subtype								[kgCO ₂ -eq/u]			[kWh oil-eq/u]		
Second basement floor	2870 x 500 x 500	n.a	n.a	4	1794	2.87	0.43 %	160	233	0.062	221	93.3	3.85
	2870 x 250 x 600	n.a	n.a	4	1076	1.72	0.26 %	95.8	140	0.037	132	56.0	2.31
	2870 x 400 x 500	n.a	n.a	3	1435	1.72	0.26 %	128	187	0.049	177	74.6	3.08
	2870 x 250 x 500	n.a	n.a	1	897	0.36	0.05 %	79.8	117	0.031	110	46.6	1.93
First basement floor	3020 x 300 x 500	n.a	n.a	5	1133	2.27	0.34 %	101	147	0.037	139	58.9	2.31
	3020 x 250 x 500	n.a	n.a	7	944	2.64	0.39 %	84.0	123	0.031	116	49.1	1.93
	3020 x 250 x 600	n.a	n.a	6	1133	2.72	0.41 %	101	147	0.037	139	58.9	2.31
Ground floor	2520 x 200 x 600	n.a	n.a	5	756	1.51	0.23 %	67.3	98.3	0.030	93.0	39.3	1.85
	2520 x 200 x 500	n.a	n.a	11	630	2.77	0.41 %	56.1	81.9	0.025	77.5	32.8	1.54
1 st floor	2520 x 200 x 350	n.a	n.a	11	441	1.94	0.29 %	39.2	57.3	0.017	54.2	22.9	1.08
	2520 x 200 x 400	n.a	n.a	1	500	0.20	0.03 %	44,5	65.0	0.020	61.5	26.0	1.23
2 nd floor	2520 x 180 x 180	n.a	n.a	11	204	0.90	0.13 %	18.2	26.5	0.008	25.1	10.6	0.5

Type SOC5904

Category: Column components

Cast-in-place columns

Additional information

Additional note	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > * The material investigations and assumptions were carried out for the cast-in-place slab components of building 59. It is assumed that the cast-in-place concrete and the steel types are the same for all components of this building. > The embodied global warming potential (in kgCO₂eq) and the grey energy (in kWh oil-eq) for fabrication and demolition of the components is calculated using their weight and the equivalent factors available in the Life Cycle Assessment KBOB database. These environmental impact indicators are calculated using a higher density for concrete, to consider the presence of reinforcement. The exact impacts due to steel are however neglected and the results may be underestimated. The considered factors are the following: Concrete for buildings (without reinforcement) - KBOB ID-Number 01.002.
Attention point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > As the columns are not directly visible, their condition and damage class could not be observed. Nevertheless, considering the condition of the other interior components, no damage is expected. > A detailed inspection and investigation have not been carried out on these components. The data should therefore be treated with caution and should be verified and investigated further in case of reuse of the components.

Type SOC5905

Category: Wall components

Cast-in-place walls

Description

Construction year	1965
Material	Cast-in-place reinforced concrete
Actual location	All floors
Initial function	Wall load-bearing component
Accessibility	Difficult – 3 & more component to dismantle before
Anchor points	None
Exposition	Inside, not exposed
Color	White in most location
Finishing	Roughcast
Overlays	Type Fixation Thickness
	Roughcast - n.a.
Connexion type	Monolithic connexion with slabs
Deconstruction tool	Diamond saw or hydro-blasting

Condition and durability

Damage assessment	100 % good
Carbonatation depth [mm]	n.a
Toxic substance	Asbestos*

Mechanical characteristics**

Concrete density (ρ_c)	2350 kg/m ³
Concrete compressive strength (f_{ck})	37 MPa
Concrete young modulus (E_{cm})	36.2 GPa
Reinforcement tensile strength (f_{sd})	300 MPa
Reinforcement young modulus (E_s)	n.a.

Component	Geometry			Inventory					Environmental impacts					
	Dimensions (H x T) [mm]	Reinforcement [mm]	Cross-section resistance [kNm]	Quantity [m]	Weight [kg/m]	Total area [m ²]	Total volume [m ³]	Volume significance	Initial production	Conventional demolition	Dismantling by sawing	Initial production	Conventional demolition	Dismantling by sawing
Subtype									[kgCO2-eq/m]			[kWh oil-eq/m]		
2 nd basement floor	2870 x 350	n.a	n.a	12.79	2511	36.7	12.85	0.64 %	224	327	0.086	309	131	5.39
	2870 x 200	n.a	n.a	7.45	1435	21.4	4.27	0.38 %	128	187	0.049	177	74.6	3.08
	2870 x 180	n.a	n.a	4.92	1292	14.1	2.54	0.46 %	115	168	0.044	159	67.2	2.77
	2870 x 160	n.a	n.a	3.77	1148	10.8	1.73	0.26 %	102	149	0.039	141	59.7	2.46
	2870 x 150	n.a	n.a	7.18	1076	20.6	3.09	1.92 %	95.8	140	0.037	132	56.0	2.31
1 st basement floor	3020 x 200	n.a	n.a	10.97	1510	33.1	6.63	0.93 %	134	196	0.049	186	78.5	3.08
	3020 x 180	n.a	n.a	32.61	1359	98.5	17.73	2.65 %	121	177	0.044	167	70.7	2.77
	3020 x 160	n.a	n.a	21.13	1208	63.8	10.21	1.53 %	108	157	0.039	149	62.8	2.46
	3020 x 150	n.a	n.a	13.69	1133	41.3	6.20	0.99 %	101	147	0.037	139	58.9	2.31
Ground, 1 st , 2 nd floors	2520 x 160	n.a	n.a	64.08	3024	161.5	25.84	3.8 %	269	393	0.118	372	157	7.39
	2520 x 180	n.a	n.a	60.1	2268	151.5	27.26	4.07 %	202	295	0.089	279	118	5.54
	2520 x 200	n.a	n.a	7.07	1260	17.8	3.56	0.53 %	112	164	0.049	155	65.5	3.08

Type SOC5905

Category: Wall components

Cast-in-place walls

Additional information

Additional note	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > * Tiles on the walls of the lift shafts may contain asbestos. > ** The material investigations and assumptions were carried out for the cast-in-place slab components of building 59. It is assumed that the cast-in-place concrete and the steel types are the same for all components of this building. > The embodied global warming potential (in kgCO₂eq) and the grey energy (in kWh oil-eq) for fabrication and demolition of the components is calculated using their weight and the equivalent factors available in the Life Cycle Assessment KBOB database. These environmental impact indicators are calculated using a higher density for concrete, to consider the presence of reinforcement. The exact impacts due to steel are however neglected and the results may be underestimated. The considered factors are the following: Concrete for buildings (without reinforcement) - KBOB ID-Number 01.002.
Attention point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > As the walls are not directly visible, their condition and damage class could not be observed. Nevertheless, considering the condition of the other interior components, no damage is expected. > A detailed inspection and investigation have not been carried out on these components. The data should therefore be treated with caution and should be verified and investigated further in case of reuse of the components.

Type SOC5906

Category: Stair components

Stairs

Description

Construction year	1965		
Material	Cast-in-place concrete		
Actual location	All floors		
Initial function	Flight of spiral stairs, self-supporting		
Accessibility	Moderate – one or two components are first removed		
Anchor points	None		
Exposition	Inside, not exposed		
Color	White paint		
Finishing	Horizontal wood plank patterns or roughcast		
Overlays	Type	Fixation	Thickness
Stair faces	Tiling	n.a.	n.a.
Lower face	Paint	-	-
Connexion type	Monolithic connection to cast-in-place slabs and walls		
Deconstruction tool	Diamond saw or hydro-blasting		

Condition and durability

Damage assessment	100 % good
Carbonatation depth [mm]	n.a
Toxic substance	Asbestos*

Mechanical characteristics**

Concrete density (ρ_c)	2350 kg/m ³
Concrete compressive strength (f_{ck})	37 MPa
Concrete young modulus (E_{cm})	36.2 GPa
Reinforcement tensile strength (f_{sd})	300 MPa
Reinforcement young modulus (E_s)	n.a

Component	Geometry			Inventory					Environmental impacts			
	Dimensions [mm]	Reinforcement [mm]	Cross-section resistance [kNm]	Quantity [u]	Weight [kg/u]	Total area [m ²]	Total volume [m ³]	Volume significance	Initial production [kgCO ₂ -eq/u]	Conventional demolition [kgCO ₂ -eq/u]	Initial production [kWh oil-eq/u]	Conventional demolition [kWh oil-eq/u]
Stair	n.a	n.a	n.a	5	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a

Additional information

Additional note	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > * The paint under the stairs may contain asbestos residues. > ** The material investigations and assumptions were carried out for the cast-in-place slab components of building 59. It is assumed that the cast-in-place concrete and the steel types are the same for all components of this building.
Attention point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Data on the stairs is very scarce. Further investigations is needed in order to get information on their exact geometry, reinforcement layouts, and material properties. > A detailed inspection and investigation have not been carried out on these components. The data should therefore be treated with caution and should be verified and investigated further in case of reuse of the components.

Type SOC5907

Category: Roof component

Timber roof structure

Location

Photos

Connection

Type SOC5907

Category: Roof component

Timber roof structure

Description

Construction year	1965
Material	Timber
Actual location	Attic
Initial function	Roof load-bearing component
Accessibility	Moderate – one or two components first removed
Anchor points	None
Exposition	Inside, not exposed
Color	Raw timber color
Finishing	Raw timber
Overlays	Type Fixation Thickness
	None - -
Connexion type	Bolted connections
Deconstruction tool	Unbolting, sawing if necessary

Condition and durability

Damage assessment	Good with some cracks
Carbonatation depth [mm]	n.a
Toxic substance	None

Mechanical characteristics

Timber density (ρ_k)	n.a
Timber compressive strength ($f_{c,0,d}$)	n.a
Timber tensile strength ($f_{t,0,d}$)	n.a
Timber bending strength ($f_{m,d}$)	n.a
Timber young modulus (E_t)	n.a

Component	Geometry		Inventory					Environmental impacts			
	Dimensions (W x T) [mm]	Cross-section resistance [kNm]	Quantity [u]	Weight [kg/u]	Total area [m ²]	Total volume [m ³]	Significance	Initial production [kgCO2-eq/u]	Conventional demolition [kgCO2-eq/u]	Initial production [kWh oil-eq/u]	Conventional demolition [kWh oil-eq/u]
Column	135 x 135	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a
Purlin	300 x 135	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a
Diagonal	125 x 125	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a

Additional information

Additional note	-
Attention point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Data on the timber structure of the roof is very scarce. Further investigations is needed in order to get information on their exact geometry and material properties. > A detailed inspection and investigation have not been carried out on these components. The data should therefore be treated with caution and should be verified and investigated further in case of reuse of the components.